

Update on available data on wild boar population and ASF epidemiology

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Abstract

An update on the available data concerning wild boar population and ecological parameters in relation to African swine fever (ASF) epidemiology is presented. Data available on wild boar population parameters included hunting statistics collected by *ENETWILD*, and wild boar occurrence at high spatial resolution based on the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). Concerning data availability on modelling the spatial distribution and abundance of wild boar, we reviewed spatial distribution models done for wild boar in Europe, indicating their main outputs and characteristics to be considered for further use in risk assessment. We also reviewed the potential use of population and risk-mediated connectivity for epidemiological studies, and their application in epidemiological studies related to wild boar and ASF; and the availability of data on scavenger communities (incl. wild boar) in Europe. Overall, recent available data on wild boar population abundance for most ASF-affected countries can be obtained from hunting statistics, which are available at high spatial resolution for some. Hunting statistics have been used to produce and validate abundance distribution models for wild boar at European level, which have been validated in mainland Europe. Recent reliable density values are scarce, but a number of them has been provided by the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), which offers the possibility to calibrate distribution model predictions (abundance) into densities that can be used in further ASF risk assessment. There exists an important body of literature quantifying spatial behaviour and population dynamic parameters over Europe which can be used in similar bioregions for individual/group-based models of disease spread. Important gaps on the relative contribution to scavenging of wild species remains in eastern Europe. Mainly, facultative scavengers are found in ASF affected countries, with low presence of obligate bird scavengers, and large predators at low numbers.

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Key words: data, wild boar, demography, density, ecology, epidemiology, African swine fever

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Summary

Background: To guide African swine fever (ASF) control policies, it is essential defining the most relevant basic parameters of wild boar population dynamics to understand them in a context-dependent manner (e. g., geography, ecological and management contexts) and to identify data gaps. This information would allow better and rapid risk assessment on the factors determining the spread and outcome of ASF infection in wild boar populations.

Objectives: This report provides an update on the available data concerning wild boar population and ecological parameters in relation to ASF epidemiology, including hunting data, wild boar movement, connectivity (degree to which a landscape facilitates or impedes the movement of focal organisms), and the description of potential scavenger communities and the wild boar/pig interfaces.

Methods: We summarised data available on wild boar population parameters at European level, which are relevant for, and included these sources:

- Occurrence: data available on wild boar occurrence at high spatial resolution (< 2km) is based on the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), which also included data submitted by ENETWILD. These data can be used to model wild boar habitat suitability.
- Abundance data: hunting statistics, collected by ENETWILD, are the most widely distributed and available data at large scale in Europe which is potentially useful to develop spatial abundance models. This is relevant to incorporate the spatial variation of wild boar population abundance into ASF risk assessment.
- Density, population demography, productivity, and structure, as well as spatial behaviour parameters (home range, dispersal): we updated a literature review carried out by ENETWILD in 2021. These data are relevant to develop spatially explicit epidemiological models of disease spread while considering social structure (at individuals and/or social group level).
- Data based on modelling the spatial distribution and abundance of wild boar, and spatial connectivity: we reviewed and summarise the spatial distribution models done for wild boar in Europe, indicating their main outputs and characteristics to be considered for further use in ecological studies, as well as methodological approaches to elaborate connectivity maps for wildlife. Model outputs (abundance, connectivity) are not primary data, as they can be obtained from distribution and abundance data, and are relevant to incorporate the spatial variation of wild boar population abundance/density and spatial connections of risks in epidemiological models
- Scavenging communities: we reviewed different sources (international organisations elaborating maps) on the distribution (presence) of the main vertebrate scavengers over Europe. When local or regional variations in scavenging communities (composition, relative abundance) are expected, this information is relevant to evaluate their contribution to wild boar carcass removal and subsequent impact on ASF spread and maintenance.

Results and discussion:

- Data available on wild boar population and ecology
 - Relative abundance (hunting statistics): Currently the hunting statistics available for wild boar at European level are, in terms of spatial coverage and resolution unpaired to other mammalian species. Hunting statistics have been essential to model the abundance and distribution of wild boar, and outputs (i.e. abundance models) obtained using hunting bags data had already been used in ASF epidemiological studies and risk assessment. However, data gaps still exist, and national hunting statistics data collection frameworks and data sharing need to improve in certain regions, and particularly, regarding the effort applied during hunting activities.
 - Density: we identified a recent increasing number of density values in literature based on potentially reliable density methods, however, still scattered and only a low number of them allows determining the local impact of ASF on wild boar population and the contribution of population parameters to disease spread maintenance and control. Camera trap-derived data, collected following common protocols and standards, as provided by the European Observatory of Wildlife (<https://eow.wildlifeobservatory.org/>), together with some available in literature, will allow calibrating the prediction of abundance distribution models shortly.
 - Population parameters (sex and age structure, productivity) and movement behaviour: although it is always desirable having data for a larger range of ecological and epidemiological scenarios, the updated literature review evidences that current data availability may well serve to sustain demographic models for wild boar, essential for modelling disease dynamics (e. g, social group, or individual based models) and control strategies.
- A recent and validated wild boar abundance distribution model at high resolution (2x2km) is available from ENETWILD and can be used to incorporate density into ASF risk assessment models. However, it requires calibration into density using reliable values as commented above. Regarding data available on wild boar connectivity: the reviewed available data and methodologies on the matter, allows for these data to be used in different epidemiological analyses concerning ASF, such as disease spread models. Connectivity analysis may address different questions related to ASF epidemiology, risk assessment and control, for which a diversity of approaches (which are here reviewed) may use already available data at international and national level.
- Wild boar population parameters and ecology in relation to ASF epidemiology: a relatively reduced number of papers on ASF epidemiology determined accurately population parameters in our reviewed literature. Most of them used abundance indexes rather than density values, which are normally not standardised and hardly useful for between-study site comparisons. Even it was low the number of reported

density values determined in ASF epidemiological studies, which often were not based on reliable methodologies, or they are not described. It is urgent to determine wild boar density in pre and post ASF scenarios.

- Scavenger spp. presence over Europe: wild boar is the dominant scavenger species over Europe, even when it is a facultative carrion consumer. In western Mediterranean areas obligate scavengers, namely vultures, become more relevant and literature supports their roles as “sanitary” agents. Even so, wild boar still has been described as an important contributor of carcass use, and even wild boar carrion/hunting remain consuming in certain scenarios, with subsequent risk for ASF spread. Important gaps on the relative contribution to scavenging of wild species remains in eastern Europe.
- Wild boar/pig interface : regarding the possibility to map the wild boar/pig interface in Europe (in spatial terms) at high resolution, European countries that collect wildlife data on their distribution and abundances use their own methodologies, resulting in differences in spatial resolution and accessibility. To create precise maps of shared disease transmission risk between wild boar and domestic pigs, it is essential to obtain higher resolution data than currently available on the distribution and abundance. Most European countries provide hunting records that can be used (once elaborated and/or modelled) as an indicator of large-scale trends, although these records are generally not uniformly available and vary in availability and resolution among countries. This situation prevents mapping the interface of wild boar with pigs at high resolution at European scale.

Overall, recent available data on wild boar population abundance for ASF affected case countries (Czechia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Slovakia, and Sweden) is available as can be obtained from hunting statistics, which are available at high spatial resolution. ENETWILD needs to make further efforts to update data for the last hunting seasons in some countries, which is currently ongoing, and new data will be available shortly. Hunting statistics have been used to produce and validate abundance distribution models for wild boar at European level at high resolution (2x2 km), which have been validated in mainland Europe. Recent and reliable density values for wild boar are scarce, both at European level, and, for the selected case countries. However, density data generated by the EOW offer the possibility to calibrate distribution model predictions into densities, which is also an activity currently developed by ENETWILD. Recent spatial behaviour parameters (home range, dispersal) are also scarce for selected ASF affected case countries, but there exists an important body of literature quantifying such parameters in other countries under similar conditions, which can potentially be used in these countries. Important gaps on the relative contribution to scavenging of wild species remains in eastern Europe. Mainly facultative scavengers are found in case ASF affected selected countries, with practical absence of obligate bird scavengers in the region, and large predators (brown bear, *Canis* spp) at low numbers. Relative abundance (not density) can be estimated locally from wild bird European monitoring programs (e. g., EuroBird Portal, <https://eurobirdportal.org/ebp/>) for birds. For mammal scavengers, the best data are hunting statistics for wild boar and red foxes (ENETWILD produced the first spatial

Available data on wild boar population and epidemiology

distribution models for some carnivore species). Good data exists on scavenger species distribution for large predators (e.g., IUCN).

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Terms of Reference

The contract entitled “Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population, and environment (framework contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01) was awarded to the Universidad of Torino by EFSA. Further, we refer to this framework contract as to *ENETWILD* project.

The specific objective 1 (SO1) of the framework contract refers “Wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment”. The deliverable 2.2A specifies to provide an update on the available data related to wild boar population and epidemiology: hunting data, camera traps data, wild boar movement, connectivity, scavengers’ presence, and others, including spatial resolution and time of collection to serve further risk factor analysis. Report is to be stored in a dedicated SharePoint provided by EFSA and discuss the results during the WG meetings on ASF (October and November 2023), and it is due by 20/10/2023.

1.2. Scope of the report

This report presents an update on the available data related to wild boar population and epidemiology, in which country and for which year these are available:

- Data available on wild boar population and ecology
 - Relative abundance: hunting statistics
 - Density
 - Demography
 - Population structure
 - Productivity
 - Data available on wild boar movement (home range, dispersal)
- Data availability on spatial distribution and abundance, and connectivity
- Data available on wild boar population parameters and ecology in relation to ASF epidemiology
- Scavenger presence: medium to big size vertebrate communities over Europe
- The wild boar/pig interface

2. METHODS

This update on the available data related to wild boar population and epidemiology is based on the following procedures:

2.1. Data available on wild boar population parameters

We summarised data available on wild boar population parameters at European level, which are relevant for, and included these sources:

- Occurrence: data available on wild boar occurrence at high spatial resolution (< 2km) is based on the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), which also included data submitted by ENETWILD. These data can be used to model wild boar habitat suitability.
- Abundance data: hunting statistics, collected by ENETWILD, are the most widely distributed and available data at large scale in Europe which is potentially useful to develop spatial abundance models. This is relevant to incorporate the spatial variation of wild boar population abundance into ASF risk assessment.
- Density, population demography, productivity, and structure, as well as spatial behaviour parameters (home range, dispersal): we updated a literature review carried out by ENETWILD in 2021. These data are relevant to develop spatially explicit epidemiological models of disease spread while considering social structure (at individuals and/or social group level).
- Data based on modelling the spatial distribution and abundance of wild boar, and spatial connectivity: we reviewed and summarise the spatial distribution models done for wild boar in Europe, indicating their main outputs and characteristics to be considered for further use in ecological studies, as well as methodological approaches to elaborate connectivity maps for wildlife. Model outputs (abundance, connectivity) are not primary data, as they can be obtained from distribution and abundance data, and are relevant to incorporate the spatial variation of wild boar population abundance/density and spatial connections of risks in epidemiological models. The wild boar spatial model for abundance based on hunting yield which we recommend for further use (at 2x2 km resolution) for all Europe representing pre-ASF scenario is available (ENETWILD-Consortium et al 2021c see figure 5 in <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6825>) at: <https://zenodo.org/records/3823926#.Xs5Jd8J7nKw> (from those, select "1_June_2020_HY_nut01_10x10_twostep.tif").

· Scavenging communities: we reviewed different sources (international organisations elaborating maps) on the distribution (presence) of the main vertebrate scavengers over Europe. When local or regional variations in scavenging communities (composition, relative abundance) are expected, this information is relevant to evaluate their contribution to wild boar carcass removal and subsequent impact on ASF spread and maintenance.

2.2. Data available on wild boar population in relation to ASF epidemiology

This section will refer to the use of wild boar population and ecological parameters but referred only to studies addressing ASF epidemiology.

Data availability on scavenger communities (incl. wild boar) in Europe: we assessed the existing knowledge on vertebrate consumption of carcasses associated to epidemiological studies by reviewing research works retrieved through a search in Web of Science (i. e. 'scaveng* AND (carcass* OR carrion) AND (epidem* OR infect* OR diseas* OR pathog* OR parasit*)' up to October 2023. From each preliminary screening (title, abstract and keywords) we extracted available information describing the typology of studies relevant to understanding disease dynamics where scavengers were involved.

We attended to studies on ecological interactions with implications for epidemiological dynamics but did not address the disease or pathogen directly. The identified interactions relevant to disease transmission (epidemiological dynamics by incorporating the study of the disease or pathogen in an active way) were identified. We recorded the main disease or pathogens involved. Finally, we present maps on the known distribution of the main scavenging species in Europe based on GBIF and IUCN.

3. DATA AVAILABLE ON WILD BOAR POPULATION PARAMETERS AND EPIDEMIOLOGY IN RELATION TO ASF

3.1. Data available on wild boar population parameters

3.1.1. Abundance data: hunting statistics

3.1.1.1 Hunting statistics collected by ENETWILD

Next, we present a detailed table (Table 1) and a map (Figure 1) on the wild boar hunting statistics collected by the ENETWILD project, indicating the temporal and spatial resolution by country.

Figure 1: Data availability of wild boar hunting bags by country and spatial resolutions shared by data providers.

Table 1: Hunting statistics collected by *ENETWILD* project since 2017, indicating the temporal and spatial resolution by country.

country/Region	Temporal availability	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution
Czech Republic	2014/2015 – 2016/2017	Hunting season	< NUTS3
Czech Republic	2017/2018 – 2021/2022	Hunting season	NUTS3
Slovakia	2010 – 2020	year	< NUTS3
Slovakia	2020/2021	Hunting season	LAU1
Bosnia and Herzegovina	No data	No data	No data
North Macedonia	2014-2011	year	Regions
Slovenia	2014-2021	year	NUTS1
Slovenia	2014-2022	year	Regions
Slovenia	2017	year	< NUTS3
Belgium	2014-2022	year	LAU2
France	1973-2016	year	NUTS3 (Departments)
France	2014/2015 -2020/2021	Hunting season	NUTS3
France	2019/2020 – 2020/2021	Hunting season	< NUTS3
Hungary	2013	year	NUTS2
Hungary	2014-2021	year	LAU2
Luxembourg	2009/2010 – 2017/2018	Hunting season	< LAU2
Portugal	1989/1990 – 2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Portugal	2012/2013 – 2020/2021	Hunting season	< NUTS3
Spain-Andalucía	2014/2015-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Aragon	2014/2015-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Asturias	2015/2016-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Cantabria	2003/2004-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
	2008/2009-2020/2021		
Spain-Castilla- La Mancha	2014/2015-2018/2019	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Castilla y León	2013/2014-2017/2018	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Cataluña	2018/2019-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground

Spain-Extremadura	2012/2013-2018/2019	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Galicia	2013/2014-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-La Rioja	2015/2016-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Madrid	2014/2015-2017/2018	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Murcia	2012/2013-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Navarra	2013/2014-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-PV-Álava	2014/2015-2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-PV-Vizcaya	2013/2014-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain- PV-Guipúzcoa	2016/2017-2017/2018	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Spain-Valencia	2017/2018-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Estonia	2013/2014-2021-2022	Hunting season	< LAU2
Estonia	2015-2021	Monthly	Hunting district
Finland	2014-2021	year	NUTS3
Lithuania	2014-2017	year	LAU1
Lithuania	2014-2019	Hunting season	District
Lithuania	2020	year	Hunting ground
Latvia	2015/2016 - 2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Poland	2015/2016 - 2021/2022	Hunting season	Municipalities
Denmark	2011/2012 - 2019/2020	Hunting season	< NUTS3
Norway	2014/2015 - 2019/2020	Hunting season	Municipalities
Sweden	2012/2013 - 2018/2019	Hunting season	NUTS3
Sweden	2019/2020 - 2020/2021	Hunting season	District
Austria	2011/2012 - 2020/2021	Hunting season	NUTS2
Germany	2012/2013 - 2020/2021	Hunting season	< NUTS3 (partial)
Germany	2011-2012-2013 (aggregated)	aggregated	NUTS3
Germany	2014-2015-2016-2017 (aggregated)	aggregated	NUTS3
Ireland	No data	No data	No data
United Kingdom	No data	No data	No data
Bulgaria	2014-2015-2016-2017-2020	year	NUTS2
Bulgaria	2018-2019	year	NUTS0

Albania	No data	No data	No data
Cyprus	No data	No data	No data
Greece	2014/2015 – 2017/2018	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Greece	2019-2020	year	NUTS1
Italy	2015-2021	year	NUTS0
Italy-Puglia	2015/2016-2020/2021	Hunting season	Comuni
Italy-Trentino	2014-2021	year	Province
Italy-Abruzzo	2015/2016-2017/2018	Hunting season	Hunting management unit
Italy-Emilia Romagna	2014/2015-2019/2020	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Emilia Romagna	2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting management unit
Italy-Lazio	2015/2016-2017/2018	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Italy-Lazio	2019/2020-2021/2022	Hunting season	Hunting management unit
Italy-Marche	2014/2015-2016/2017	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Toscana	2019/2020-2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Italy-Umbria	2020/2021	Hunting season	Province
Italy- Veneto	2017/2018-2019/2020	Hunting season	Province
Italy- Veneto	2019/2020-2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Italy- Veneto	2021/2022	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Italy-Basilicata	2014/2015-2019/2020	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Basilicata	2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting management unit
Italy-Calabria	2019/2020-2020/2021	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Calabria	2021/2022	Hunting season	Municipalities
Italy-Campania	2018/2019	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Campania	2019/2020 – 2020/2021	Hunting season	Municipalities
Italy-Friuli-Venezia-Giulia	2019/2020-2021/2022	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Italy-Liguria	2020/2021	Hunting season	Municipalities
Italy-Liguria	2020/2021	Hunting season	Management unit
Italy-Liguria	2014/2015-2020/2021	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Imperia	2014/2015-2019/2020	Hunting season	Province

Italy-La Spezia	2014-2019	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Italy-Savona	2014/2015 – 2018/2019	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Lombardia	2021	year	Province
Italy-Lombardia	2022	year	Province
Italy-Molise	2014/2015-2017/2018	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Piemonte	2015/2016-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting management unit
Italy-Piemonte	2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting management unit
Italy-Puglia	2015/2016-2020/2021	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Trentino	2014-2020	Hunting season	Province
Italy-Trentino	2020	year	Trentino regions
Italy-Trentino	2019 – 2021	year	Hunting management unit
Italy-Valle d’Aosta	2014/2015-2021/2022	Hunting season	Valle d’Aosta regions
Turkey	No data	No data	No data
Croatia	2015-2018	year	NUTS1
Croatia	2018/2019-2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Croatia	2021/2022	Hunting season	NUTS2
Montenegro	2016/2017-2019/2020	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Montenegro	2016-2018	year	NUTS3
Serbia	2015-2017 & 2019-2021	year	NUTS0
Serbia	2014	year	NUTS3
Moldova	2018	year	Municipalities
Romania	2016/2017-2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Netherlands	2019 & 2021	year	Regional

Regarding the monitoring of wild boar population monitoring in the framework of current ASF outbreak in Europe, the Ministerial Conference (Agriculture) held in Brussels on (DEC 2018) stated that, all Member States, where appropriate, should put their efforts to ensure:

- Enhanced coordination and cooperation between agricultural and environmental side (veterinary services, farmers, forestry management bodies, hunters and etc.) to regulate wild boar populations with the objective of both to efficiently control and prevent the spreading of ASF

- A long-term EU management strategy of wild boar population, including its appropriate reduction.

The EU member states committed to develop national action plans on wild boar management in the context of ASF prevention, control, and eradication, which should align with the strategic approach on ASF management for the EU. The plans should adapt to national priorities and specific contexts. Within the frame of II Annual General meeting (ENETWILD-consortium 2020), we asked representatives of EU countries to characterise the national plans in relation to: (i) the approach to build the plan (e. g. which administrations, sectors, stakeholders have participated), and (ii) which specific measures have been included (variability, adaptation to local contexts, mutual learning). The figure 2 displays the interviewed countries, including 9 countries plus 2 regions, which included 5 non ASF countries and 6 affected areas (countries or regions in 2020).

Figure 2: The interviewed countries (left, in colour), including 9 countries plus 2 regions (right), which included 5 non ASF countries and 6 affected areas (countries or regions in 2020).

About wild boar population monitoring, the following graph (Figure 3) summarises (% of positive responses) the methods included in the plans to monitor wild boar populations. It is evident in this sample that annual hunting bags are the preferred approach (100% of interviewed countries), while lower proportions considered also more reliable methods, such as high-quality hunting statistics (including hunting effort and efficacy), camera trapping to estimate density or abundance.

Figure 3: The graph summarises (% of positive responses) the methods included in the national plans to monitor wild boar populations.

3.1.2. Data availability on wild boar population and ecological parameters: density, demography, population structure, productivity and spatial behaviour

To guide ASF control policies, it is essential defining the most relevant basic parameters of wild boar population dynamics (which is highly variable) to understand them in a context-dependent manner (e. g., geography, ecological and management contexts) and to identify data gaps. This information would allow better harmonised monitoring of wild boar populations and the impacts of ASF management actions, so as parametrizing population dynamics and epidemiological models to develop most efficient cost-benefit strategies. This section updates a previous report (*ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022c*) and presents a comprehensive compilation and description of parameters on wild boar population dynamics, including general drivers, population demography, mortality, reproduction, and spatial behaviour. The table 5 summarises the parameters describing the basic aspects of WB population dynamics relevant to understanding disease dynamics and improving science-

based ASF management. The complete list of selected articles is presented as an electronic appendix (D.2.2. Wild boar review.xlsx), including where and when data are available.

Table 2: List of parameters describing the basic aspects of WB population dynamics relevant to understanding disease dynamics and improve science-based ASF management. Colours of "trait" column indicate the priority of each parameter to be determined (orange: high; yellow: medium; green: low).

Populati on paramet ers	Trait	Sex by age class	Temporal	Spatial resoluti on	Units	Why is important?	Ref	
Populatio n characte ristics	Local density		Optimally pre-harvest season (for standardizatio n)	Manage ment or ecologic al unit	ind/km ² or social group/km ²	-Disease transmission is a density-dependent process. Population and individual traits are density dependent. Management is based on numbers (abundance indexes are not sufficient or comparable) -It could further elucidate complex species-habitat-management relationships in spatial distribution models	Kramer-Schadt et al. 2009	
	Absolute abundance				No individuals		Yu et al. 2020	
	Carrying capacity		Lowest over the year	Ecologic al unit	maximu m populati on size or density (K)	-Variable due to habitat perturbations and environmental factors (e.g, resource availability and climate). Theoretically, maximum productivity (i.e, population growth rate) is achieved when the population is approx. 50% of the K (basic logistic growth models). Useful for modelling scenarios of potential population growth and consequences for disease spread, maintenance and control.	Groot Bruinderink et al. 1994	
	Sex ratio		juvenile (< 1 y)	Optimally pre-harvest season (for standardization)		ff:mm	-Essential to rebuild population structure and model population dynamics -Influence on the spatial behaviour and interactions among social units (groups) and modulate the spread of infectious diseases	Hema et al. 2020; Mortensen et al. 2016
			yearling (1-2 y)					
			adult (> 2 y)					
	Group size		male	average annual and by month or season	Manage ment or ecologic al unit	mean number of individuals, assumed 1	-Each sex by age class has distinct properties in terms of their demographic and infection dynamics -Key parameters to define population control strategy -These parameters are among those presenting larger variation over geographical distribution and management	Loehle, 1995; Pepin et al. 2020; Podgórski et al. 2018
			maternal groups			mean number of individuals		
	Age structure		By sex	Pre-harvest season		%		Hoy et al. 2020
	Populatio n growth rate			yearly		% or increase rate (r)		Fonseca et al. 2011

	Recruitment rate				coefficient of young/adult		DeCesare et al. 2012
Population characteristics: mortality	Natural: predation/disease	Sex by age. Especially on piglets (<3 months old)	yearly		% mortality (1/survival)		Bassi et al. 2020; Keuling et al. 2013; Lange et al. 2012; Merli et al. 2017; Tanner et al. 2019b
	By harvest						
	Other: e.g, road kills						
Reproduction (productivity)	Litter size	By age*	yearly		Number of offspring born by female age class		Fernández-Llario & Mateos-Quesada, 1998; Frauendorf et al. 2016
	Pregnant females		yearly and monthly				
Spatial behaviour	Proportion of dispersants	Sex by age	yearly		%	-Related with species geographical and disease dispersion. -Spatial behaviour determines interactions (within and among groups) -Spatial behaviour is relevant to implement effective management strategies.	Casas-Díaz et al. 2013; Truvé & Lemel, 2003; Truvé et al. 2004
	Dispersal period	Sex by age					
	Dispersal distance						
	Home range (50 & 95%K)	Sex by age (males, maternal groups)	seasonal	km	km ²	- Influenced by land uses and human activities among other factors, including population control and response to ASF	Bisi et al. 2018; Enetwild consortium 2018

Regarding data available on spatial behaviour, wild boar parameters can be used to model disease spread and maintenance by incorporating within and between social groups contacts, and this can be spatially explicit. Therefore, We present a literature review on wild boar movement parameters (namely home range, dispersal, habitat, and resource selection) in European territory, including grey literature, which updates the literature review (using the same procedures) published in 2022 (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022c). The complete list of selected articles and movement parameters are presented as an electronic appendix in excel.

In the future, we will evaluate a potential collaboration with EUROBOAR (<https://euromammals.org/euroboar/>), by creating a specific pager to assess the potentiality of the EUROBOAR network to increase the availability of useful data for better estimation of wild boar movement parameters. The following figure presents the number of tracked (telemetry) wild boar per study areas in Europe, and specifically, in countries of interest compiled by partners of EUROBOAR (November 2023).

Figure 4: Number of tracked (telemetry) wild boar per study areas in Europe, and specifically, in countries of interest, compiled by EUROBOAR.

3.1.3. Data availability on wild boar occurrence

These data are based on the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, <https://www.gbif.org/es/>), an international network and data infrastructure providing open

access to data about all types of life on Earth. The approach is similar to that on the scavenger species, which will also include wild boar (see below). We retrieved the existing records (a total of 57623) available at GBIF for the period 2010-2022 with a spatial resolution better than 2000 metres, which are considered suitable for spatial modelling their distribution (see map in Figure 10). Data are available at <https://api.gbif.org/v1/occurrence/download/request/0022226-231002084531237.zip> (Citation: GBIF.org (20 October 2023) GBIF Occurrence Download <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.j9q35w>).

Figure 5: Wild boar existing records (a total of 57623) available at Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) for the period 2010-2022 with a spatial resolution better than 2000 metres, which are considered suitable for spatial modelling their distribution.

Other data sources on wild boar occurrence needs to be evaluated, such as locations of ASF cases and roadkill locations. These data, if considered suitable (quality of georeferentiation and adequate validation) to be included in the dataset of wild boar occurrences, will be harmonised accordingly. It is possible to incorporate this new information from alternative data sources, since records of collisions of wild boar and other ungulates with vehicles are recorded in many regions. This may decrease the potential for modelling species distribution and abundance (e. g., Fernández-López et al 2022). However, a centralised and harmonised data collection system does not exist in Europe and thus information is rarely openly available at high resolution. Therefore, future efforts are needed (i) to identify national /regional wildlife roadkill data sources, and (ii) to standardise them.

In those countries where ASF has arrived, a system of collection and testing of samples from wild boar found dead is maintained with adequate temporal and spatial resolution allowing incorporate information about wild boar and disease occurrence (e. g. Podgorski et al 2019). Most of this information is entered into National Competent Veterinary Authorities that report to the EU´s Animal Diseases Information System (ADIS) and WAHIS (World Animal Health Information System) from the World Organisation for Animal Health. In Europe, EFSA also collect records of the laboratory data obtained on ASF samples on wild boar.

3.1.5. Data availability on spatial distribution and abundance models for wild boar, and connectivity.

This section summarises existing models for predicting the spatial distribution and abundance of wild boar at various scales (European, national and regional) in order to inform on usable best estimates of wild boar abundance at European level. We also include the modelling developed by *ENETWILD* since 2018, which has been considered a continuous activity that improved over time thanks to increasing availability of high resolution and more complete data on hunting statistics, as well as the development and application of novel analytical methodology to cope with available data and gaps. We include expert occurrences data (presence-absence and presence-background), hunting bag data and density data. The Annex 1 summarises existing models for distribution and abundance of wild boar at European, national, and regional level.

The wild boar spatial model for abundance based on hunting yield which we recommend for further use (at 2x2 km resolution) for all Europe representing pre-ASF scenario is available (ENETWILD-Consortium et al 2021c see figure 5 in <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6825>) at: <https://zenodo.org/records/3823926#.Xs5Jd8J7nKw> (from those, select "1_June_2020_HY_nut01_10x10_twostep.tif").

As for connectivity, it has been studied from very different perspectives, and therefore many definitions have been used to explain this biological process. In general, we can state that connectivity is the degree to which a landscape facilitates or impedes the movement of focal organisms (Taylor et al. 1993). The different metrics that have been used to measure such phenomena can be broadly differentiated in a gradient between structural connectivity and functional connectivity. Metrics based on structural connectivity study the physical location of habitat patches within the non-habitat matrix. On the other hand, metrics based on functional connectivity considers also the matrix surrounding the suitable habitat patches (Keeley et al. 2021). Following this, we could differentiate (Figure 6) among:

- Structural connectivity metrics derived from binary maps and species-nonspecific spatial functions: Starting from a map of patches of suitable habitat within a matrix of homogeneous non-habitat, they use simple metrics such as the Euclidean distance to the nearest habitat or the suitable area in a radius of a focal patch to measure the connectivity between patches.
- Structural connectivity metrics derived from binary maps and species-specific population sizes and dispersal functions: Similar to the previous ones, but they include one or two elements of functional connectivity, such as species-specific population sizes in each patch, or estimated dispersal distances for the studied species.
- Resistance-based connectivity metrics: Here, the non-habitat matrix is replaced by one or multiple raster which characterise the landscape between habitat patches. Then, an algorithm is used to quantify how much the cell impedes or promotes the species movement as a function of landscape attributes. Finally, a cost-weighted movement flow can be computed from this resistance layer among the different habitat patches.
- Complex functional connectivity metrics: A common factor of previous metrics is that they model rather than observe actual presence or behaviour of individuals in the landscape. Complex functional connectivity metrics benefit from direct observations of patch occupancy or their related components (extinction, colonisation, persistence, etc) to assess connectivity among different locations. Gene flow or movement of individuals between patches derived from GPS data can reflect successful movement and reproduction over time.

- Key metrics**
- Distance to nearest (occupied) habitat patch
 - Area of suitable habitat within focal patch buffer
- Key concepts**
- Discrete patches of habitat are embedded in a uniform matrix of non-habitat
 - Metrics consider patch sizes and inter-patch distances

- Key metrics**
- Incidence Function Measure
 - Flux
- Key concepts**
- Discrete patches of habitat are embedded in a uniform matrix of non-habitat
 - Metrics incorporate 1 or 2 elements of functional connectivity, e.g., species-specific population size in each patch, or dispersal distances of focal species.

Figure 6: Representation of the different connectivity metrics. A) Structural connectivity metrics derived from binary maps and species-nonspecific spatial functions; B) Structural connectivity metrics derived from binary maps and species-specific population sizes and dispersal functions; C) Resistance-based connectivity metrics; D) Complex functional connectivity metrics. Adapted from Keeley et al. (2021).

- Application in epidemiological studies

Connectivity plays a key role in the spread and persistence of wildlife diseases. Host behaviours, movements or contact patterns, influence disease spread over a landscape or a region (Craft 2015). Thus, it is necessary to understand those factors shaping host connectivity to implement effective measures to control new outbreaks or disease

transmission. For example, a detailed analysis of white-tailed deer *Odocoileus virginianus* connectivity based on resistance metrics in Colorado, USA, allowed to focus surveillance efforts along river valleys surrounded by agriculture to control chronic wasting disease outbreaks (Nobert et al. 2016). In southern California, a combined analysis including connectivity layers and agent-based models identified that an intermediate level of non-habitat permeability will result in the highest rates of feline immunodeficiency virus transmission in bobcats *Lynx rufus* (Tracey et al. 2014). Not only wildlife, but also livestock connectivity mapping can be useful for disease risk control (Ekwem et al. 2021). These examples confirm the importance of connectivity analysis to improve preventive surveillance as well as to implement quick responses for outbreaks control.

- Proposals for further risk assessment in relation to wild boar and ASF

Previous work developed by the *ENETWILD* has led to a robust knowledge about wild boar distribution and abundance in Europe (*ENETWILD*-consortium et al. 2021c). Wild boar relative abundance maps can be used to build resistance maps for pathogen transmission by using the inverse of the spatially explicit model predictions. Over this layer (relative abundance maps), algorithms such as circuit theory (McRae 2006) or other methods such as agent-based models (Gochanour et al. 2021) can be implemented to compute connectivity between different locations or across the continuous landscape.

GPS data could also inform wild boar movement behaviour and connectivity at local scale, allowing quick responses in specific new outbreak areas. *EUROBOAR* project (<https://euromammals.org/euroboar/>) is a research network that promotes wild boar GPS data shearing among institutions to better understand movement ecology in those animals.

EUROBOAR is financed from the bottom up by donations from members, so the financial aspects of this relationship need to be assessed. The main steps are signing the 'Terms of use', submitting a pager (which is basically a request for data to potential data providers- i.e. *EUROBOAR* members - outlining the data needs, analyses, outputs, timeline). Assessment of the viability of the proposal and willingness of data providers to participate in it.

The main advantages are that a database is enriched with telemetry data by different sources from different regions of Europe; and many *ENETWILD* partners have contributed their data to *EUROBOAR*. (e. g., IREC, MRI, ITAW...), and are part of the network.

EUROBOAR partners are the owner of the data, so they decide if they contribute or not to the specific proposals. Depending on the source and hypotheses. The data may need a deep

curation which is time consuming, and a dedicated person to manage the data, conduct the analyses (once we know what we actually need) and interact with *EUROBOAR* (basically, lead the pager). Therefore, the information available and spatial coverage is conditioned by researcher objectives and constraints .

3.2. Data available on wild boar population in relation to ASF epidemiology

This section includes the use of wild boar population and ecological parameters (referred in previous section) in literature on ASF, as well as a review of species potentially scavenging on wild boar carcasses, and therefore, relevant to ASF epidemiology and control.

3.2.1 Data available on wild boar population in relation to ASF epidemiology

We indicated the use of wild boar population and ecological parameters in the reviewed literature in the attached excel (indicated as 1 in column "epidemiological study ASF"). At least 42 references on ASF epidemiology determined population parameters, accounting for 128 specific determinations (different populations) of such parameters (ranging from density to relative abundance to population structure, productivity, or spatial behaviour). When determining wild boar abundance (in a broad sense), most of them used abundance indexes (N=67 values), which are normally not standardised and hardly useful for between-study comparisons, while density values were recorded in 24 cases, only in one case through a reliable method (REM, Palencia et al. 2023). The density values require case by case evaluation of their reliability (see *ENETWILD-consortium 2018a, 2020b, 2021a, 2021b* for recommended methods for density estimation by *ENETWILD*).

3.2.2. Scavenger community

We reviewed different sources (international institutions and initiatives) of data on the distribution (presence and abundance) of the main vertebrate scavengers over Europe. These data can be useful to consider their contribution to wild boar carcass removal and subsequent impact on ASF spread and maintenance. We assessed the existing knowledge on vertebrate consumption of carcasses associated to epidemiological studies in Europe by reviewing research references retrieved through a search in Web of Science (i. e. 'scaveng* AND (carcass* OR carrion) AND (epidem* OR infect* OR diseas* OR pathog* OR parasit*)' up to October 2023. About 283 records were identified through database searching, and 190 records were selected after title and abstract screening (the selected studies are distributed between 1991 and 2023 with a marked growth over the last 10 years).

From each preliminary screening (title, abstract and keywords) we extracted available information describing the typology of studies relevant to understanding disease dynamics where scavengers were involved. Ecological interaction included papers that addressed the study of scavenger communities with implications for epidemiological dynamics, but without addressing the disease or pathogen directly.

- Disease interactions: it refers to epidemiological dynamics by incorporating the study of the disease or pathogen in an active way.
- Other interactions or approaches: these articles addressed the issue from complementary or indirect approaches such as social, toxicological, status and other aspects, probably less relevant to studying epidemiological dynamics.
- In addition, we recorded the main pathogens involved.

Interactions with diseases is the most frequently addressed topic, followed by studies focusing on ecological interactions (Figure 7). The diseases or pathogens that received most attention (Figure 8) were *Trichinella*, *Mycobacterium*, *Anthrax*, *Salmonella*, closely followed among

others, by ASF, indicating the interest of studying scavenging activities in relation to wild boar and ASF.

Figure 7: Number of papers by approximation addressing scavengers and epidemiological studies.

Figure 8: Main diseases or pathogens involved in the disease interactions with scavengers.

The selection of scavenger species is based on the work of Mateo-Tomás et al (2015) which reviewed published literature where systematic monitoring was used to assess the structure of the scavenger communities.

The different species can be classified following the next criteria:

1. Raptors on the top of the web, apex predators.
2. Carnivore raptors of medium size, in general, are predators.
3. Vultures, obligate scavengers, primarily feed on carrion and are thus adapted to efficiently locate and access animal carcasses.
4. Birds residing in marine environments exhibit omnivorous feeding habits.
5. Omnivorous birds with low occurrence rates (<1%) in a single location.
6. Medium-sized carnivorous raptors have the capability to hunt and kill their prey but also frequently rely on carrion.
7. Medium to large-sized passerines with an omnivorous diet that includes small vertebrates, invertebrates, plant material and carrion.
8. Small to medium-sized omnivorous mammals that feed on plant material, invertebrates, small vertebrates, and carrion Cannibalism (through carrion consumption) is also reported.
9. Mammals of small to medium size (<15 kg) have a diet that primarily consists of meat (50-70%), supplemented with non-vertebrate foods including arthropods, fungi, fruits, and other plant material.
10. Small to medium-sized (<15 kg) carnivorous mammals form another category.
11. Large mammals (≥ 15 kg) at the top of food webs. Most of these species are obligate meat eaters.

However, there are also some omnivorous (and even one herbivorous) species (e. g, wild boar, bears; Ripple et al, 2014).

3.2.3. Mapping the wild boar/pig interface in Europe

As for wildlife, European countries that collect data on their abundances use their own methodologies, resulting in differences in spatial resolution and accessibility. To create precise maps of shared disease transmission risk between wildlife and domestic animals, it is essential to obtain higher resolution data than currently available on the distribution and abundance of different species, as emphasized by *ENETWILD*-consortium et al. (2021d). For wild ungulates, most European countries provide hunting records that can be used (once elaborated and/or modelled) as an indicator of large-scale trends, although, these records are generally not uniformly available and vary in availability and resolution among countries (*ENETWILD*-

consortium et al, 2018). Livestock distribution and census data is variably available in Europe, depending on the country, which prevents from mapping the interface with wildlife at high resolutions over large spatial range (ENETWILD-consortium et al, 2021d). The currently available official census data of livestock at the European Union level is limited to the spatial resolution at NUTS2 (Eurostat, 2023).

3.2.3.1 Large scale characterization of the interface in Europe

Local-scale approaches rely on precise data, such as the GPS-tagged locations of both wild and domestic animals (e. g., Triguero-Ocaña et al, 2021). On the other hand, large-scale approaches often utilise more widely available data but with lower precision and resolution, often aggregated (e. g, at administrative level, ENETWILD-consortium et al, 2021d).

The model of the interface based on the data from Gridded Livestock of the World (GLW) database of FAO provides predictions on a 1×1 km scale globally (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2020). The present available census data of livestock at the European Union level (Eurostat) is restricted to a maximum spatial resolution of NUTS2, remarking the need of developing a framework to collect harmonised data with higher resolution. Eurostat complies and makes available at website the livestock density by NUTS 2 regions for EU28, the latest, for 2016 (livestock units per hectare utilised agricultural area). Other sources of pig population data in eastern Europe identified by FAO (<http://www.fao.org/3/a-ak755e.pdf>).

Eurostat provides the livestock density index, which measures the stock of animals (cattle, sheep, goats, Equidae pigs, poultry and rabbits) converted in livestock units (LSUs) per hectare of utilised agricultural area (UAA).

To define the spatial interface between wild boar and domestic pigs in Europe, the ENETWILD consortium (ENETWILD- Consortium et al. 2020) preliminarily assessed the spatial interface between pigs and wild boar over Europe using the best quality data available (Eurostat data and ENETWILD spatial models), distinguishing pig production types in countries where data was available. The projection of the interface, in terms of spatial overlapping between wild boar abundance distribution and pig farm locations at high special resolution was only possible (as examples) in certain countries for which high spatial resolution data was available for domestic pigs. Based on comparisons at different scales and quality of data, it was proposed future steps in both data collection and modelling approach: precise spatial resolution of pig data is not available at European level yet, and the discrimination of extensive vs. intensive farms, backyards vs. commercial; outdoor vs. indoor, is essential to quantify and perform risk analyses separately for each production system and/or considering this relevant source of variation in risk at the interface.

In a further step, ENETWILD (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2021d), including also other than EUROSTAT sources data for livestock, presented an analysis of the spatial overlapping between the distribution of livestock and wild ungulates at highest possible and relatively similarly sized administrative level to date. This was to provide a general picture of Europe

(using relatively similar-sized regions), or preliminary risk maps of ungulate species assemblages and possible interfaces, compiling for the first time, comprehensive data for both groups. They depicted their spatial overlapping over Europe for different ungulate pair wildlife-domestic species, including wild boar and pigs. While this analysis was purely spatial and at administrative level, the interface between wild and domestic ungulates is influenced by livestock husbandry (e. g, enclosed, herded or free-ranging, level of biosecurity), landscape and land use, and wildlife management practices, among other factors, operating locally. Therefore, there is a need for a more detailed picture of the interface at European scale (as commented above, only some examples at national level are available).

3.2.3.2 Interactions at the interface at local scale

Presence of wild boar in pig farms could relate to farm type and resource access (external biosecurity), such as food or water points. It has been determined that proximity of forest to the farm and distance between pig enclosures and houses (where farmers live) are factors that influence WB intrusions (Wu et al. 2012; Kukielka et al. 2013). Moreover, physical barriers such as fences of minimum height or electrified fences could be measures to reduce or avoid direct WB-pig interactions. Even though direct contact is uncommon (Cadenas-Fernández et al. 2019; Triguero-Ocaña et al. 2020), indirect contact could be an important factor in disease transmission (Kukielka et al, 2013). It has been found that WB are generally more attracted to sows in oestrus than to other resources such as food (Wu et al. 2012; Wyckoff et al. 2009). Thus, mating purposes could be a factor of attraction for the WB to the pig farms.

Most research on the study of the interface at local level has been developed in western Mediterranean areas and western Europe (e. g. Triguero-Ocaña et al. 2021, Cadenas-Fernández et al. 2019, Jori et al. 2022, Jori et al. 2017). Recent research (ENETWILD - Consortium 2023) described (i) the use of extensive pig farm resources by wildlife (wild boar and other mammals) and domestic pigs, and (ii) the factors involved. The study focused on two regions of Central-Eastern Europe with contrasted outdoor management of pigs, Serbia, in low biosecurity farms on forestall/bushland habitats, and Hungary, characterised by more professional farming in fenced pastures.

Contact rates at intra-specific and between species have potential to be used in disease spread models. It is remarkable that only two study attempted to estimate the frequency of contacts between wild boar and pig in extensive systems using methodological approach capable to determine them with precision (telemetry: proximity loggers; Cowie et al, 2016; Triguero-Ocaña et al. 2021). In this work authors aimed to study the interactions between domestic

(cattle and Iberian pigs) and wild (red deer and wild boar) ungulates coexisting in free-ranging production systems, characterising for the first time the potential relevance of different domestic and wild species in the transmission of pathogens during a critical period in these systems, such as the montane (mast) period. To this end, they used GPS technology at a high spatiotemporal resolution. Specifically, this research aimed (i) to quantify the frequency of interaction among species as a potential source of cross-transmission of pathogens and (ii) to explore temporal and spatial patterns in the interaction frequency. In this study, it was detected and estimated the frequency of interaction as a proxy of the real interactions taking place in the study area.

3.3. Data available on wild boar population in EU ASF affected countries for further risk assessment

A summary of available data and studies on wild boar hunting statistics, density estimations (using methodology considered as potentially reliable and comparable), movement behaviour (home range and dispersal), and description of communities scavenging on carcasses/hunting remains is provided in next tables. As for connectivity (see section above for definitions and methodologies), studies specifically focused on wild boar are absent, but it can be estimated from different sources of data (abundance/distribution models, movement behaviour parameters), i.e., this is secondary spatial data that can be generated at different spatial scales using primary data.

The Table 3 shows the hunting statistics collected by the ENETWILD since 2017, indicating the temporal and spatial resolution by case country.

Table 3: Hunting statistics collected by *ENETWILD* project since 2017, indicating the temporal and spatial resolution by country.

country/Region	Temporal availability	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution
Czech Republic	2014/2015 – 2016/2017	Hunting season	< NUTS3
Czech Republic	2017/2018 – 2021/2022	Hunting season	NUTS3
Slovakia	2010 – 2020	year	< NUTS3
Slovakia	2020/2021	Hunting season	LAU1
Hungary	2013	year	NUTS2
Hungary	2014-2021	year	LAU2
Lithuania	2014-2017	year	LAU1
Lithuania	2014-2019	Hunting season	District
Lithuania	2020	year	Hunting ground
Latvia	2015/2016 – 2020/2021	Hunting season	Hunting ground
Sweden	2012/2013 – 2018/2019	Hunting season	NUTS3
Sweden	2019/2020 – 2020/2021	Hunting season	District
Italy	2015-2021	year	NUTS0

The following table (Table 4) summarises available potentially reliable density estimates by method and previous lustrum per country (more details for each reference can be found in appendix excel, see ENETWILD-Consortium 2022).

Table 4: Available and potentially reliable density estimates by method and previous lustrum per country. The ASF entrance column indicates the year of disease emergence (see ENETWILD-Consortium 2022).

Density method	ASF entrance	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2021-2023
Czech Republic	2017								
Camera trapping: counts in feeding sites									
Faecal counts							1		
REM									2
Hungary	2018								
REM									1
Italy (mainland)	2022								
CMR				45				1	
CMR feeding points					5	5			
Distance sampling			1	6	5	5			
Drive counts		3	9		1	3	5	10	
Faecal counts								8	
REM							1		6
Latvia	2014								
Estimated by hunters (considered not reliable)							1	5	1
Lithuania	2014								
REM									1
Slovakia	2019								
REM									1
Sweden	2023								
REM									1

Available density estimates by method and previous lustrum, ASF value indicates the year of African Swine Fever emergence. REM: Random Encounter Model by photo-trapping Model. CMR: capture-mark-recapture. For details on the methods, see *ENETWILD-consortium et al.*

2018a. Next, Table 5 shows the available spatial behaviour studies in scientific literature for case Countries.

Table 5: Available Spatial behaviour studies by country and lustrum.

country	1980	1985	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2023
Czech Republic										
Hungary									1	
Italy			1	3		3	4		5	
Latvia										
Lithuania										
Slovakia										
Sweden										

The Table 6 summarises the data on the presence of scavengers by country (case countries plus Poland) obtained from GBIF (number of records). Maps on existing records available at GBIF) for the period 2010-2022 showing a spatial resolution better than 2000 metres (suitable for modelling their distribution) can be generated at GBIF website. This information can be complemented with the distribution maps provided by the IUCN (<https://www.iucnredlist.org/resources/spatial-data-download>).

Table 6: Summary of data on presence of scavenger by country (case countries plus Poland) obtained from Global Biodiversity Information Facility GBIF (number of records in selected countries). Those potentially more relevant, based on their ability to scavenge more biomass (remove infected material) are indicated with *, which corresponds to groups 1 to 3, and 11 of the abovementioned classification of scavengers.

Species	Scientific Name	CZ	HU	IT	LT	LV	PL	SE	SK
2433433	<i>Ursus arctos</i> *	1	0	18	0	0	45	40	66
2433875	<i>Meles meles</i>	12	17	626	22	3	125	4212	6
2434255	<i>Herpestes ichneumon</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2434532	<i>Alopex lagopus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
2434552	<i>Nyctereutes procyonoides</i>	1	0	0	13	3	88	429	1

2435240	<i>Lynx lynx</i>	3	0	1	1	1	5	0	7
2435261	<i>Lynx pardinus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2477968	<i>Dendrocopos major</i>	1005	705	1396	369	186	1110	497639	69
2480389	<i>Gyps fulvus</i> *	2	0	316	0	0	0	372	0
2480446	<i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
2480449	<i>Haliaeetus albicilla</i>	249	693	4	233	156	921	473818	21
2480482	<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>	277	1715	1137	225	165	780	321572	67
2480506	<i>Aquila chrysaetos</i> *	1	1	607	2	3	6	45181	23
2480510	<i>Aquila adalberti</i> *	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2480537	<i>Buteo buteo</i>	697	2061	3486	261	272	546	554928	97
2480589	<i>Accipiter gentilis</i>	43	10	176	6	43	21	134145	7
2480649	<i>Gypaetus barbatus</i> *	0	0	113	0	0	1	2	0
2480696	<i>Neophron percnopterus</i> *	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
2480830	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	4	51	1332	0	0	0	1044	1
2482492	<i>Corvus corax</i> *	196	150	1093	364	228	491	357335	50
5218878	<i>Martes martes</i>	15	6	106	7	3	59	2885	3
5218887	<i>Martes foina</i>	25	10	233	2	3	31	49	1
5218987	<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	13	10	51	5	0	21	1549	8
5219019	<i>Mustela erminea</i>	10	2	45	2	0	7	1313	2
5219073	<i>Gulo gulo</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0
5219173	<i>Canis lupus</i> *	10	0	45	2	0	60	2	4
5219200	<i>Canis familiaris</i> *	6	0	16	1	0	1	1	1
5219219	<i>Canis aureus</i> *	0	3	3	1	0	1	3	0
5219243	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i> *	51	108	1401	174	13	972	17055	36
5219362	<i>Genetta genetta</i>	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0

5229165	<i>Aegypius monachus</i> *	0	1	0	0	0	0	7	0
5229167	<i>Milvus migrans</i> *	29	16	861	5	8	39	21804	4
5229168	<i>Milvus milvus</i> *	209	3	318	6	2	124	209927	11
5229490	<i>Pica pica</i>	667	612	2451	379	163	342	414352	75
5229493	<i>Garrulus glandarius</i>	814	255	2159	179	173	533	251689	60
5844449	<i>Aquila fasciata</i>	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0
5959092	<i>Bubo bubo</i>	82	30	37	0	3	0	7148	8
7341881	<i>Cyanopica cyanus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7705930	<i>Sus scrofa</i> *	55	28	1031	46	0	414	6134	38
8069880	<i>Falco rusticolus</i>	1	0	0	0	0	0	3650	0
8211070	<i>Sciurus vulgaris</i>	588	133	895	159	13	866	28600	42
8316400	<i>Sorex araneus</i>	25	2	0	5	1	18	1702	0
9409796	<i>Corvus corone</i>	59	17	721	3	3	9	322698	8
9533902	<i>Felis silvestris catus</i>	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0

Finally, we summarise all relevant data availability for the selected countries in Table 16. The list of selected countries include those EU countries affected by ASF that have submitted laboratory data on wild boar sampling to EFSA with the maximum geographical resolution .

Table 7: Summary of all relevant data availability in selected ASF affected countries (case countries). Connectivity is not included as no specific data for wild boar exist, however it is secondary data that can be obtained from other sources. Abundance of wild boar based on hunting yield model prediction is available for all countries (2x2 km), as well as suitability based on occurrence data.

country	Hunting statistics	Density (n° values 2015-)	Spatial behaviour, 2010- (n° studies)	Scavenging community
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Czechia	District, whole country	3		<p>Mainly facultative scavengers, practical absence of obligate bird scavengers in the region, large predators (brown bear, <i>Canis</i> spp) at low numbers. Relative abundance (not density) can be estimated locally from wild bird European monitoring programs (e. g., EBP). For mammals, best data are hunting statistics for wild boar and red foxes. Good data on species distribution for large predators, but low relevance as scavengers. Number and distribution of obligate bird scavengers increasing in Italy.</p>
Hungary	Hunting ground, whole country	1	1	
Italy	Variable, not whole country covered	31	9	
Lithuania	Hunting ground, whole country	1		
Latvia	Hunting ground, whole country	0		
Slovakia	District (LAU1), all country	1		
Sweden	District, all country	1		

Overall, recent available data on wild boar population abundance for ASF affected case countries (Czechia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Slovakia, and Sweden) is available as can be obtained from hunting statistics, which are available at high spatial resolution (Figure 1, Table 16). ENETWILD needs to make further efforts to update data for the last hunting seasons in some countries, which is currently ongoing, and new data will be available shortly. Hunting statistics have been used to produce and validate abundance distribution models for wild boar at European level at high resolution (2x2 km), which have been validated in mainland Europe. Recent and reliable density values for wild boar are scarce, both at European level, and in particular, for the selected case countries. However, density data generated by the EOW offer the possibility to calibrate distribution model predictions into densities, which is also an activity currently developed by ENETWILD. Recent spatial behaviour parameters (home range, dispersal) are also scarce for selected ASF affected case countries, but there exists an important body of literature quantifying such parameters in other countries under similar conditions, which can potentially be used in these countries. Important gaps on the relative contribution to scavenging of wild species remains in eastern Europe. Mainly facultative scavengers are found in case ASF affected selected countries, with practical absence of obligate bird scavengers in the region, and large predators (brown bear,

Canis spp) at low numbers. Relative abundance (not density) can be estimated locally from wild bird European monitoring programs (e. g., EuroBird Portal, <https://eurobirdportal.org/ebp/>) for birds. For mammal scavengers, the best data are hunting statistics for wild boar and red foxes (ENETWILD produced the first spatial distribution models for some carnivore species). Good data exists on scavenger species distribution for large predators (e.g., IUCN).

4. DISCUSSION

- Data available on wild boar population and ecology
 - Relative abundance (hunting statistics): no database compares to current availability of hunting data for wild boar in Europe in terms of spatial coverage and resolution. Hunting statistics have been essential to model the abundance and distribution of wild boar, and high resolution outputs has already been used in ASF epidemiological studies and risk assessment. However, data gaps still exist, and national hunting statistics data collection frameworks and data sharing need to improve in certain regions, and particularly, regarding the effort applied during hunting activities.
 - Density: we identified an increasing number of density values in literature based on potentially reliable density methods, however, still scattered and only a low number of them allows determining the local impact of ASF on wild boar population and the contribution of population parameters to disease spread maintenance and control. The values provided by the European Observatory of Wildlife (<https://eow.wildlifeobservatory.org/>), together with those available at literature, will allow calibrating the prediction of abundance distribution models shortly.
 - Demography, population structure and productivity: although it is always desirable having data for a larger range of ecological and epidemiological scenarios, the literature review evidences that current availability may well serve to sustain demographic models for wild boar, essential for modelling disease dynamics (e.g., social group, or individual based models) and control strategies.
- The wild boar spatial model for abundance based on hunting yield which we recommend for further use (at 2x2 km resolution) for all Europe representing pre-ASF scenario is available (ENETWILD-Consortium et al 2021c see figure 5 in <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6825>) at: <https://zenodo.org/records/3823926#.Xs5Jd8J7nKw> (from those, select "1_June_2020_HY_nut01_10x10_twostep.tif"). Connectivity analysis may address different questions related to ASF epidemiology, risk assessment and control, for which a diversity of approaches (which are here reviewed) may use already available data at international level.

- Wild boar population parameters and ecology in relation to ASF epidemiology (literature review): a relatively reduced number of papers on ASF epidemiology accurately determined population parameters. Most of them used abundance indexes rather than density values, which are normally not standardised and are hardly useful for between-study site comparisons. Even it was even lower the number of reported density values determined in ASF epidemiological studies, which often were not based on reliable methodologies, or they were not described. It is urgent to determine wild boar density in pre and post ASF scenarios.
- Scavenger spp. presence: wild boar is the dominant scavengers species over Europe, even when it is a facultative carrion consumer. In western Mediterranean areas obligate scavengers, namely vultures, become more relevant and literature supports their roles as “sanitary” agents. Even so, wild boar still has been described as an important contributor of carcass use, and even wild boar carrion/hunting remain consuming in certain scenarios, with subsequent risk for ASF spread. Important gaps on the relative contribution to scavenging of wild species remains in eastern Europe.
- Wild boar/pig interface: regarding the possibility to map the wild boar/pig interface in Europe (in spatial terms) at high resolution, European countries that collect wildlife data on their distribution and abundances use their own methodologies, resulting in differences in spatial resolution and accessibility. To create precise maps of shared disease transmission risk between wildlife and domestic animals, it is essential to obtain higher resolution data than currently available on the distribution and abundance. For wild boar and other ungulates, most European countries provide hunting records that can be used (once elaborated and/or modelled) as an indicator of large-scale trends, although these records are generally not uniformly available and vary in availability and resolution among countries. Livestock distribution and census data is variably available in Europe, depending on the country, which prevents from mapping the interface with wildlife at high resolution.
- Overall, recent available data on wild boar population abundance for ASF affected case countries (Czechia, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Slovakia, and Sweden) is available as can be obtained from hunting statistics, which are available at high spatial resolution ENETWILD needs to make further efforts to update data for the last hunting seasons in some countries, which is currently ongoing, and new data will be available shortly. Hunting statistics have been used to produce and validate abundance distribution models for wild boar at European level at high resolution (2x2 km), which have been validated in mainland Europe. Recent and reliable density values for wild boar are scarce, both at European level, and in particular, for the selected case countries. However, density data generated

by the EOW offer the possibility to calibrate distribution model predictions into densities, which is also an activity currently developed by ENETWILD. Recent spatial behaviour parameters (home range, dispersal) are also scarce for selected ASF affected case countries, but there exists an important body of literature quantifying such parameters in other countries under similar conditions, which can potentially be used in these countries. Important gaps on the relative contribution to scavenging of wild species remains in eastern Europe. Mainly facultative scavengers are found in case ASF affected selected countries, with practical absence of obligate bird scavengers in the region, and large predators (brown bear, *Canis spp*) at low numbers. Relative abundance (not density) can be estimated locally from wild bird European monitoring programs for birds. For mammal scavengers, the best data are hunting statistics for wild boar and red foxes (ENETWILD produced the first spatial distribution models for some carnivore species). Good data exists on scavenger species distribution for large predators (e.g., IUCN).

5. REFERENCES

- Acevedo P, Quirós-Fernández F, Casal J, Vicente J, (2014). "Spatial distribution of wild boar population abundance: basic information for spatial epidemiology and wildlife management." *Ecological Indicators* 36: 594-600.
- Acevedo P, Farfán MA, Márquez AL, Delibes-Mateos M, Real R, Vargas JM, (2011). "Past, present and future of wild ungulates in relation to changes in land use." *Landscape Ecology* 26: 19-31.
- Alexander NS, Massei G, Wint W (2016). "The European distribution of *Sus scrofa*. Model outputs from the project described within the poster - where are all the boars? An attempt to gain a continental perspective." *Open Health Data* 4(1).
- Allepuz A, Hovari M, Masiulis M, Ciaravin, G, Beltrán-Alcrudo, D, (2022). Targeting the search of African swine fever-infected wild boar carcasses: A tool for early detection. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 69(5), e1682-e1692.
- Ansell C, Gash A, (2008). Collaborative governance in theory and practice. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 18(4), 543-571.
- Belda A, Oltra-Cresp, S, Miro-Martinez P, Zaragoza B, (2020). Can spatial distribution of ungulates be predicted by modelling camera trap data related to landscape indices? A case study in a fragmented Mediterranean landscape. *CALDASIA*, 42(1), 96-104.
- Böhm M, Hutchings MR, White PCL, (2009). Contact networks in a wildlife-livestock host community: Identifying high-risk individuals in the transmission of bovine TB among badgers and cattle. *PLoS One*, 4(4), e5016.
- Boklund A, Dhollander S, Chesnoiu Vasile T, Abrahantes JC, Bøtner A, Gogin A, Gonzalez Villeta LC, Gortázar C, More SJ, Papanikolaou A, van der Stede, Y, Mortensen S. (2020). Risk factors for African swine fever incursion in Romanian domestic farms during (2019). *Scientific Reports*, 10(1).
- Bosch J, Torre ADL, Alexandrov T, Iglesias I, Miteva A, Muñoz MJ (2014a). "Can habitat suitability predict the presence of wild boar? Suitable land uses vs. georeferenced data in Bulgaria." *Folia Zoologica* 63(3): 194-205.
- Bosch J, Mardones F, Pérez A, de la Torre A, Muñoz AJ, (2014b). "A maximum entropy model for predicting wild boar distribution in Spain." *2014* 12(4): 16.

- Bosch J, Iglesias I, Muñoz MJ, de la Torre A, (2017). "A cartographic tool for managing African swine fever in Eurasia: mapping wild boar distribution based on the quality of available habitats." *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases* 64(6): 1720-1733.
- Bosch J, Peris S, Fonseca C, Martinez M, Torre ADI, Iglesias I, Muñoz MJ, (2012). "Distribution, abundance and density of the wild boar on the Iberian Peninsula, based on the CORINE program and hunting statistics." *Folia Zoologica* 61(2): 138-151.
- Cadenas-Fernández E, Sánchez-Vizcaíno JM, Pintore A, Denurra D, Cherchi M, Jurado C, Vicente J, Barasona JA, (2019). Free-Ranging Pig and Wild Boar Interactions in an Endemic Area of African Swine Fever. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 6.
- Carrasco-García R, Barasona JA, Gortázar C, Montoro V, Sanchez-Vizcaino JM, Vicente J, (2016). Wildlife and livestock use of extensive farm resources in South Central Spain: Implications for disease transmission. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 62(1), 65–78.
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/605 of 7 April 2021 laying down special control measures for African swine fever (Text with EEA relevance). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L129, 7th April 2021 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R0605&from=EN>
- Cowie CE, Hutchings MR, Barasona JA, Gortázar C, Vicente J, White PCL, (2016) Interactions between four species in a complex wildlife: livestock disease community: implications for *Mycobacterium bovis* maintenance and transmission. *European Journal of Wildlife Research* 62 (1), 51–64.
- Craft ME, (2015). Infectious disease transmission and contact networks in wildlife and livestock. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 370(1669), 20140107.
- Croft S, Chauvenet ALM, Smith GC, (2017). "A systematic approach to estimate the distribution and total abundance of British mammals." *PLoS ONE* 12(6): e0176339.
- Croft S, Massei G, Smith GC, Fouracre D, Aegerter JN, (2020). Modelling Spatial and Temporal Patterns of African Swine Fever in an Isolated Wild Boar Population to Support Decision-Making. *FRONTIERS IN VETERINARY SCIENCE*, 7.
- DG SANTE, Directorate General for Health and Food Safety Strategic Approach to the Management of African Swine Fever for the EU. [(accessed on 9 November

2020)];2015 SANTE/7113/2015-Rev 12. Available online:
https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/animals/docs/ad_control-measures_asf_wrk-doc-sante-2015-7113.pdf

- Economov VA, Kolesnikov VV, Mashkin IV, Lissovsky AA, (2020). Using spatial data on habitat suitability in estimation of wild boar (*Sus scrofa* L.) resources in Russia. *Baltic Forestry*, 26(2), 193-201.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), Baños, JV, Boklund A, Gogin A, Gortázar C, Guberti V, Helyes G, Kantere M, Korytarova D,, Annick L, Marius M, Miteva A, Neghirla IN, Oļševskis E, Ostojic S, Satran P, Staubach C, Thulke H, Arvo V, Wozniakowski G, Broglia A, Abrahantes Cortiñas J, Dhollander S, Mur L, Papanikolaou A, Van der Stede Y, Zancanaro G, Ståhl K, (2022). Epidemiological analyses of African swine fever in the European Union: (September 2020 to August 2021). *EFSA Journal*, 20(5), e07290.
- EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), Boklund A, Bøtner A, Chesnoiu T, Depner K, Desmecht D, Guberti V, Helyes G, Korytarova D, Linden A, Miteva A, More S, Olsevskis E, Ostojic S, Roberts H, Spiridon M, Ståhl K, Thulke H, Vilija G, Viltrop A, Wallo R, Wozniakowski G, Abrahantes-Cortiñas J, Dhollander S, Gogin A, Ivanciu C, Papanikolaou A, González-Villela Lau C, Gortázar C, (2020). Epidemiological analyses of African swine fever in the European Union (November 2018 to October 2019). *EFSA Journal*, 18(1).
- EFSA AHAW Panel (EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare), Nielsen SS, Alvarez J, Bicout DJ, Calistri P, Canali E, Drewe JA, Garin-Bastuji B, Gonzales Rojas JL, Herskin M, Miranda Chueca MA, Michel V, Padalino B, Pasquali P, Roberts HC, Sihvonen LH, Spoolder H, Stahl K, Velarde A, Viltrop A, Winckler C, Blome S, More S, Gervelmeyer A, Antoniou S-E and Gortazar Schmidt C, 2021. Scientific Opinion on the African swine fever and outdoor farming of pigs. *EFSA Journal* 2021;19(6):6639, 113 pp
- EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare (AHAW Panel) (2009). "Guidance on good practice in conducting scientific assessments in animal health using modelling." *EFSA Journal* 7(12): 1419.
- EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare (AHAW Panel), More S, Miranda MA, Bicout D, Bøtner A, Butterworth A, Calistri P, Edwards S, Garin-Bastuji B, Good M, Michel V., Raj M, Saxmose Nielsen S, Sihvonen L, Spoolder H, Stegeman JA, Velarde A, Willeberg P, Winckler C, Depner K, Guberti V, Masiulis M, Olsevskis E. Satran P, Spiridon M,

- Thulke H, Vilrop A, Ozniakowski G, Bau A, Broglia A, Cortiñas Abrahantes J, Dhollander S, Gogin A, Muñoz Gajardo I, Verdonck F, Amato L, Gortázar Schmidt C, (2018). "Scientific Opinion on the African swine fever in wild boar." *EFSA Journal* 16(7):5344, 78 pp.
- EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare (AHAW), Nielsen, SS, Alvarez J, Bicout, DJ, Calistri P, Canali E, Drewe JA, Garin-Bastuji B, Gonzales Rojas J, Herskin M, Miranda Chueca MÁ, Michel V, Padalino B, Pasquali P, Roberts HC, Sihvonen LH, Spoolder H, Stahl K, Velarde A, Viltrop A, Gortázar Schmidt C. (2021). African swine fever and outdoor farming of pigs. *EFSA Journal*, 19(6).
 - EFSA Panel on Animal Health and Welfare (AHAW). (2014). Scientific Opinion on African swine fever. In *EFSA Journal* (Vol. 12, Issue 4). Wiley-Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
 - EFSA Panel on Plant Protection Products and their Residues (PPR Panel) (2014). "Scientific Opinion on good modelling practice in the context of mechanistic effect models for risk assessment of plant protection products." *EFSA Journal* 12(3): 3589.
 - Ekwem D, Morrison TA, Reeve R, Enright J, Buza, J, Shirima G, Hopcraft, JGC, (2021). Livestock movement informs the risk of disease spread in traditional production systems in East Africa. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 16375
 - ENETWILD-Consortium, Vicente J, Plhal R, Blanco-Aguilar JA, Sange M, Podgórski T, Petrovic K, Scandura M, Cohen Nabeiro A, Body G, Keuling O, Apollonio M, Ferroglio E, Zanet S, Brivio F, Smith GC, Croft S, Acevedo P, R Soriguer, (2018). Analysis of hunting statistics collection frameworks for wild boar across Europe and proposals for improving the harmonisation of data collection. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 15(12), 1523E.
 - ENETWILD-consortium, Keuling O, Sange M, Acevedo P, Podgorski T, Smith G, Scandura M, Apollonio M, Ferroglio E, Body G, Vicente J, (2018a). Guidance on estimation of wild boar population abundance and density: methods, challenges, possibilities. *EFSA supporting publication* 2018:EN-1449.
 - ENETWILD-Consortium, Croft S, Smith G, Acevedo P, Vicente J, (2019). Wild boar in focus: Review of existing models on spatial distribution and density of wild boar and proposal for next steps. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 15(10).
 - ENETWILD-consortium, Acevedo P, Croft S, Smith G, Vicente J, (2019a). ENETWILD modelling of wild boar distribution and abundance: initial model output based on

hunting data and update of occurrence-based models. EFSA Supporting Publications, 16(5).

- ENETWILD-consortium, Acevedo P, Croft S, Smith GC, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Fernandez-Lopez J, Scandura M, Apollonio M, Vicente J, (2019b). ENETWILD modelling of wild boar distribution and abundance: update of occurrence and hunting data-based models. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 16(8), 1674E.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Fernandez-Lopez J, Acevedo P, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Vicente J, (2020). Analysis of wild boar-domestic pig interface in Europe: preliminary analysis. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 17(4), 1834E.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Acevedo P, Croft S, Smith G, Blanco-Aguiari JA, Fernández-López J, Scandura M, Apollonio M, Ferroglio E, Keuling O, Sange M, Zanet S, Brivio F, Podgorski T, Petrovic K, Soriguer R, Vicente J, (2020a). Update of occurrence and hunting yield-based data models for wild boar at European scale: new approach to handle the bioregion effect. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 17(5), 1871E.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Grignolio S, Apollonio M, Brivio F, Vicente J, Acevedo P, Palencia P, Petrovic K, Keuling O, (2020b). Guidance on estimation of abundance and density data of wild ruminant population: methods, challenges, possibilities. EFSA supporting publication 2020:EN-1876.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Acevedo P, Apollonio M, Bevilacqua C, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Brivio F, Casaer J, Ferroglio E, Grignolio S, Jansen P, Illanas S, Kavčić K, Keuling O, Palencia P, Plis K, Podgórski T, Rowcliffe M, Ruiz C, Smith G, Scandura M, Soriguer R, Šprem, N, Vada R, Zanet S, Vicente J, (2021a). A practical guidance on estimation of European wild ungulate population density. ENETWILD Consortium, Spain, IREC.
- ENETWILD-consortium (2021b). Data generated by camera trapping in at least 15 areas in Europe including East and South Europe: Report of the field activities February 2021a, EFSA supporting publication 2021:EN-6771.
- ENETWILD-consortium, Illanas S, Croft S, Smith GC, Fernández-López J, Vicente J, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Pascual-Rico R, Scandura M, Apollonio M, Ferroglio E, Keuling O, Zanet S, Brivio F, Podgorski T, Plis K, Soriguer R, Acevedo P, (2021c). Update of hunting yield-based data models for wild boar and first models based on occurrence for wild ruminants at European scale. EFSA Supporting Publication 2021:EN-6825.

- *ENETWILD*-consortium, Illanas S, Fernández-López J, Acevedo P, Apollonio M, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Brivio F, Croft S, Ferroglio E, Keuling O, Plis K, Podgórski T, Scandura M, Smith GC, Soriguer R, Šprem N, Zanet S, Vicente J, (2021d). Analysis of wild boar-domestic pig interface in Europe: spatial overlapping and fine resolution approach in several countries. EFSA Supporting Publications, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-1995>.
- *ENETWILD*-consortium, Acevedo P, Aleksovski V, Apollonio M, Berdión O, Blanco-Aguiar JA, del Rio L, Ertürk A, Fajdiga L, Escribano F, Ferroglio E, Gruychev G, Gutiérrez I, Häberlein V, Hoxha B, Kavčić K, Keuling O, Martínez-Carrasco C, Palencia P, Pereira P, Plhal R, Plis K, Podgórski T, Ruiz C, Scandura M, Santos J, Sereno J, Sergeyev A, Shakun V, Soriguer R, Soyumert A, Sprem N, Stoyanov S, Smith GC, Trajçe A Urbani N, Zanet S and Vicente J, (2022a). Wild boar density data generated by camera trapping in nineteen European areas. EFSA supporting publication 2022:EN-7214.
- *ENETWILD*-consortium, Illanas S, Croft S, Smith GC, López-Padilla S, Vicente J, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Scandura M, Apollonio M, Ferroglio E, Zanet S, Vada R, Keuling O, Plis K, Podgorski T, Brivio F, Fernández-López J, Ruiz-Rodríguez C, Soriguer RC, Acevedo P, (2022b). New models for wild ungulates occurrence and hunting yield abundance at European scale. EFSA Supporting Publications, 19(10), 7631E.
- *ENETWILD*-consortium, Pascual-Rico R, Acevedo P, Apollonio M, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Body G, del Rio L, Ferroglio E, Gomez A, Keuling O, Plis K, Podgórski T, Preite L, Ruiz-Rodríguez C, Scandura M, Sebastian M, Soriguer R, Smith GC, Vada R, Zanet S, Vicente J, Carpio A, (2022c). Wild boar ecology: a collection of wild boar ecological and population dynamics parameters by bioregion all over Europe. 2022:EN-7211. 27pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7211
- *ENETWILD*-consortium, López-Padilla S, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Acevedo P, Mario Sebastian M, Preite L, Illanas S, Gómez A, Fernández-López J, & Vicente J, (2023). *ENETWILD* data exploration tool (*ENETWILD*-DET): Manual to visualize and download wildlife population data (5.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8214450>
- *ENETWILD*-consortium, Sebastián-Pardo M, Laguna E, Csányi S, Gacic D, Katona K, Mirceta J, Bennedek Z, Beltrán Alcrudo D, Terjek Z, Biró Z, Schally G,, Márton M, Hózensteiner M, Fitos G, Scandura M, Apollonio M, Ferroglio E, Preite L, Hovari M, Blanco-Aguiar JA, Vicente J, (2023a). Assessment of the factors that determine the

presence of wild boars near outdoor and extensive pig farms in Eastern Europe. EFSA Supporting Publications 2023:EN-8015. 87 pp.

- Ekwem D, Morrison T A, Reeve R, Enrigh J, Buza J, Shirima G, Hopcraft JGC, (2021). Livestock movement informs the risk of disease spread in traditional production systems in East Africa. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 16375.
- Fanelli A, Perrone A, Ferroglio E, (2021). Spatial and temporal dynamics of wild boars *Sus scrofa* hunted in Alpine environment. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 67(3).
- Fernández-López J, Blanco-Aguilar JA, Vicente J, Acevedo P, (2022). Can we model distribution of population abundance from wildlife-vehicles collision data? *Ecography*, 2022(5).
- Gamelon M, Nater C. R, Baubet E, Besnard A, Touzot, L, Gaillard JM, Lebreton JD, Gimenez O, (2021). Efficient use of harvest data: A size-class-structured integrated population model for exploited populations. *Ecography*, 44(9), 1296-1310.
- Hart A, Rowe G, Bolger F, Colson A, (2021) Expert knowledge elicitation on African Swine Fever and outdoor farming of pigs. EFSA supporting publication 2021:EN-6595. 229pp.doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2021.EN-6595.
- Jiménez-Ruiz S, Laguna E, Vicente J, García-Bocanegra I, Martínez-Guijosa J, Cano-Terriza D, Risalde MA, Acevedo P, (2022). Characterization and management of interaction risks between livestock and wild ungulates on outdoor pig farms in Spain. *Porcine Health Management*, 8, 1-14.
- Jordt AM, Lange M, Kramer-Schadt S, Nielsen LH, Nielsen SS, Thulke HH, Vejre H, Alban L, (2016). "Spatio-temporal modelling of the invasive potential of wild boar - a conflict-prone species - using multi-source citizen science data." *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 124, 34-44.
- Jori F, Petit G, Civil N, Decors A, Charrier F, Casabianca F, Grosbois V, (2022). A questionnaire survey for the assessment of wild-domestic pig interactions in a context oedema disease outbreaks among wild boars (*Sus scrofa*) in South-Eastern France. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases* 69, 4009-4015.
- Jori F, Relun A, Trabucco B, Charrier F, Maestrini O, Chavernac D, Cornelis D, Casabianca F, Etter EMC, (2017). Questionnaire-based assessment of wild boar/domestic pig interactions and implications for disease risk management in Corsica [Article]. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 4(DEC), Article 198.

- Kafley H, Lamichhane BR, Maharjan R, Thapaliya B, Bhattarai N, Khadka M, Gompper ME, (2019). Estimating prey abundance and distribution from camera trap data using binomial mixture models. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 65(5).
- Karami P, Tavakoli S, (2022). Identification and analysis of areas prone to conflict with wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) in the vineyards of Malayer County, western Iran. *Ecological Modelling*, 471.
- Keeley AT, Beier P, Jenness JS, (2021). Connectivity metrics for conservation planning and monitoring. *Biological Conservation*, 255, 109008.
- Keuling O, Baubet E, Duscher A, Ebert C, Fischer C, Monaco A Podgórski T, Prevot C, Ronnenberg K, Sodeikat G, Stier N, Thurfjell H, (2013). Mortality rates of wild boar *Sus scrofa* L. in central Europe. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 59, 805-814.
- Keuling O, Stier N, Roth M, (2008a). Annual and seasonal space use of different age classes of female wild boar *Sus scrofa* L. *European Journal of Wildlife Research*, 54(3), 403-412
- Keuling O, Stier N, Roth M, (2008b). How does hunting influence activity and spatial usage in wild boar *Sus scrofa* L.? *European Journal of Wildlife research*, 54, 729-737.
- Kukielka E, Barasona JA, Cowie, CE, Drewe JA, Gortázar C, Cotarelo I, Vicente J, (2013). Spatial and temporal interactions between livestock and wildlife in South Central Spain assessed by camera traps. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 112(3-4), 213-221.
- LaHue NP, Vicente J, Acevedo P, Gortázar C, MMartínez-López B. (2016). "Spatially explicit modelling of animal tuberculosis at the wildlife-livestock interface in Ciudad Real province, Spain." *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 128, 101-111.
- Mateo RGT, Croat B, Felicísimo AM, Muñoz J, (2010). "Profile or group discriminative techniques? Generating reliable species distribution models using pseudo-absences and target-group absences from natural history collections." *Diversity and Distributions* 16(1), 84-94.
- Mateo-Tomás P, Olea PP, Moleón M, Vicente J, Botella F, Selva N, Viñuela J, Sánchez-Zapata JA, (2015). From regional to global patterns in vertebrate scavenger communities subsidized by big game hunting. *Diversity and Distributions*, 21(8), 913-924.

- Mateo-Tomás P, Olea PP, Sánchez-Barbudo IS, Mateo R (2012). "Alleviating human-wildlife conflicts: identifying the causes and mapping the risk of illegal poisoning of wild fauna." *Journal of Applied Ecology* 49(2), 376-385.
- McCallum H, Fenton A, Hudson PJ, Lee B, Levick B, Norman R, Perkins SE, Viney M, Wilson AJ, Lello J, (2017). Breaking beta: Deconstructing the parasite transmission function. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 372(1719), 20160084.
- McRae BH, (2006). Isolation by resistance. *Evolution*, 60(8), 1551-1561.
- Melis C, Szafrńska PA, Jędrzejewska B, Bartoń K, (2006). "Biogeographical variation in the population density of wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) in western Eurasia." *Journal of Biogeography* 33(5), 803-811.
- Miguel E, Grosbois V, Caron A, Boulinier T, Fritz H, Cornélis D, Foggin C, Makaya PV, Tshabalala PT, de Garine-Wichatitsky M, (2013). Contacts and foot and mouth disease transmission from wild to domestic bovines in Africa. *Ecosphere*, 4(4), 1-32.
- Morera-Pujol V, Mostert PS, Murphy KJ, Burkitt T, Coad B, McMahon BJ, Nieuwenhuis, M, Morelle K, Ward AI, Ciuti S. (2023): Bayesian species distribution models integrate presence-only and presence-absence data to predict deer distribution and relative abundance. *Ecography*, 2023(2), e06451.
- Nikolov IS, Stoeckle BC, Markov G, Kuehn R, (2017). Substantial hybridisation between wild boars (*Sus scrofa scrofa*) and East Balkan pigs (*Sus scrofa* f. *domestica*) in natural environment as a result of semi-wild rearing in Bulgaria. *Czech Journal of Animal Science*, 62, 1-8.
- Nibert BR, Merrill EH, Pybus M.J, Bollinger, TK, Hwang YT, (2016). Landscape connectivity predicts chronic wasting disease risk in Canada. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 53(5), 1450-1459.
- Ostrom E, (2009). A general framework for analyzing sustainability of social-ecological systems. *Science*, 325(5939), 419-422.
- Palencia P, Vada R, Zanet S, Calvini M, De Giovanni A, Gola G, Ferroglio E, (2023). Not just pictures: utility of camera trapping in the context of African Swine fever and wild boar management. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 2023, 1-9.

- Phillips SJ, Dudík M, (2008). "Modelling of species distributions with MaxEnt: new extensions and a comprehensive evaluation." *Ecography* 31(2), 161-175.
- Phillips SJ, Anderson RP, Schapire RE, (2006). "Maximum entropy modelling of species geographic distributions." *Ecological Modelling* 190, 231-259.
- Pittiglio C, Khomenko S, Beltran-Alcrudo D, (2018). "Wild boar mapping using population-density statistics: From polygons to high resolution raster maps." *PLoS ONE* 13(5): e0193295.
- Podgórski T, Apollonio M, Keuling O, (2018). Contact rates in wild boar populations: Implications for disease transmission. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*, 82(6), 1210-1218.
- Podgorski T, Borowik T, Lyjak M, Wozniakowski G, (2019). Spatial epidemiology of African swine fever: Host, landscape, and anthropogenic drivers of disease occurrence in wild boar. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 177. 104691
- Razenkova E, Dubinin M, Pidgeon AM, Hobi M L, Zhu L, Bragina EV, Allen AM, Clayton MK, Baskin LM, Coops NC, Radeloff VC, (2023). Abundance patterns of mammals across Russia explained by remotely sensed vegetation productivity and snow indices. *Journal of Biogeography*, 50(5), 932-946.
- Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the area of animal health ('Animal Health Law') (Text with EEA relevance) *Official Journal of the European Union*, L84, 31th March 2016.
- Ruiz-Rodríguez C, Fernández-López J, Vicente J, Blanco-Aguilar JA, Acevedo P, (2022). Revisiting wild boar spatial models based on hunting yields to assess their predictive performance on interpolation and extrapolation areas. *Ecological Modelling*, 471.
- Salazar LG, Rose N, Brandon Hayes, Pachka Hammami, Eric Baubet, Stephanie Desvaux, Mathieu Andraud, (2022). Effects of habitat fragmentation and hunting activities on African swine fever dynamics among wild boar populations, *Preventive Veterinary Medicine* 208
- Taylor PD, Fahrig L, Henein K, Merriam G, (1993). Connectivity is a vital element of landscape structure. *Oikos*, 571-573.

- Tracey JA, Bevins SN, VandeWoude S, Crooks KR, (2014). An agent-based movement model to assess the impact of landscape fragmentation on disease transmission. *Ecosphere*, 5(9), 1-24.
- Triguero-Ocaña R, Barasona JA, Carro F, Soriguer RC, Vicente J, Acevedo P, (2019). Spatio-temporal trends in the frequency of interspecific interactions between domestic and wild ungulates from Mediterranean Spain. *PLoS One*, 14(1), e0211216.
- Triguero-Ocaña R, Laguna E, Jiménez-Ruiz S, Fernández-López J, García-Bocanegra I, Barasona JÁ, Risalde MÁ, Montoro V, Vicente J, Acevedo P, (2021). The wildlife-livestock interface on extensive free-ranging pig farms in central Spain during the “montanera” period. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 68(4), 2066–2078.
- Triguero-Ocaña R, Martínez-López B, Vicente J, Barasona JA, Martínez-Guijosa J, Acevedo P, (2020). Dynamic network of interactions in the wildlife-livestock interface in mediterranean spain: An epidemiological point of view. *Pathogens*, 9(2), 120.
- Vajas P, Calenge C, Gamelon M, Girard F, Melac O, Chandosne C, Richard E, Said S, Baubet E. (2021). Catch-effort model used as a management tool in exploited populations: Wild boar as a case study. *Ecological Indicators*, 124, 107442.
- Vargas Amado MEV, Gruetter R, Fischer C, Suter S, Bernstein A. (2020). Free-ranging wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) in Switzerland: Casual observations and model-based projections during open and closed season for hunting. *Schweizer Archiv fur Tierheilkunde*, 162(6), 365-376.
- Vercauteren KC, Gortázar C, Beltrán-Alcrudo D, Vicente J. (2020). Host Community Interfaces: The Wildlife-Livestock. In: *Diseases at the Wildlife - Livestock Interface Research and Perspectives in a Changing World* Editors: Joaquín Vicente, Kurt C. Vercauteren, Christian Gortázar. Springer. Pages 3-32.
- Vicente J, Höfle U, Garrido JM, Fernández-De-Mera IG, Acevedo P, Juste R, Barral M, Gortazar C. (2007). Risk factors associated with the prevalence of tuberculosis-like lesions in fenced wild boar and red deer in south central Spain. *Veterinary Research*, 38(3), 451–464.
- Vilaça ST, Biossa D, Zachos F, Iacolina L, Kirschning J, Alves PC, Paule L, Gortazar C, Mamuris Z, Jędrzejewska B, Borowik T, Sidorovich VE, Kusak J, Costa S, Schley L, Hartl GB, Apollonio M, Bertorelle G, Scandura M, (2014). "Mitochondrial

phylogeography of the European wild boar: the effect of climate on genetic diversity and spatial lineage sorting across Europe." *Journal of Biogeography* 41(5), 987-998.

- EUROSTAT, (2023): https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/AGR_R_ANIMAL__custom_1274263/default/table?lang=en
- Wevers J, Beenaerts N, Casaer J, Zimmermann F, Artois T, Fattebert J, (2021). Modelling species distribution from camera trap by-catch using a scale-optimized occupancy approach. *Remote Sensing in Ecology and Conservation*, 7(3), 534-549.
- Williams DM, Quinn ACD, Porter WF, (2014). Informing disease models with temporal and spatial contact structure among GPS-collared individuals in wild populations. *PLoS One*, 9(1), e84368
- Woodroffe R, Donnelly CA, Chapman K, Ham C, Moyes K, Stratton NG, Cartwright SJ, (2021). Successive use of shared space by badgers and cattle: implications for *Mycobacterium bovis* transmission. *Journal of Zoology*, 314, 132-142.
- Wu N, Abril C, Thomann A, Grosclaude E, Doherr M, Boujon P, Ryser-Degiorgis M, (2012). Risk factors for contacts between wild boar and outdoor pigs in Switzerland and investigations on potential *Brucella suis* spill-over. *BMV Veterinary Research*, 8, Article ARTN 116.
- Wyckoff A, Henke S, Campbell T, Hewitt D, VerCauteren K, (2009). Feral swine contact with domestic swine: a serologic survey and assessment of potential for disease transmission. *Journal of Wildlife Diseases*, 45, 422-429.

Glossary:

Connectivity: degree to which a landscape facilitates or impedes the movement of target organisms.

European Observatory for Wildlife: a network of observation points to generate and provide information and unbiased trends on population abundance with common population estimation protocols and data collection standards to facilitate harmonization and interoperability (www.wildlifeobservatory.org).

ANNEX 1. Summary of existing models for distribution and abundance of wild boar.

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
Acevedo et al. (2011)	Hunting bag (local counts reduced to binary classification); Environment (land use, topology, spatial location)	SDM (Favourability Function)	100m resolution map of favourability (analogous to relative abundance) across Andalusia	Cross validation; AUC (0.81); Kappa (0.44); Sensitivity (0.7); Specificity (0.76)	SDM could be included in suite considered by ensemble	Availability of accurate absence data to complement presences (although pseudo-absence could be used)
Bosch et al. (2012)	Land cover (CORINE); Hunting bag (Regional counts)	Expert classification of classes assigned values 0 (unsuitable), 1 or 2 (most suitable) to identify suitable land converted to density by redistribution of hunt bag returns at regional scale	High resolution maps of relative abundance at regional level across Iberian Peninsula	Comparison with sightings data	Validation of data driven model	Lack of repeatability and flexibility to incorporate new information from data collection.
Bosch et al. (2014a)	Land cover (CORINE)	Expert classification of classes assigned values 0 (unsuitable), 1 or 2 (most suitable)	High resolution map of classified suitability across Bulgaria	Comparison with sightings data	Validation of data driven model	Lack of repeatability and flexibility to incorporate new information from

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
						data collection
Bosch et al. (2014b)	Species presence-only (GBIF); Environment (climate, topography, land cover, solar radiation, anthropogenic)	SDM (MaxEnt)	10km resolution map of relative suitability across Spain	Cross validation; AUC (0.79)	Already included as part of suite of SDMs in ensemble	Accurate definition of model extent from which background is selected – species range & survey extent
Acevedo et al. (2014)	Hunting bag (estates); Environment (spatial, climate, land use)	Regression using a GLM with negative binomial distribution and logarithmic link function; 3 approaches : all estates, bioregion as factor, separate bioregion models	10km resolution map of classified abundance (7 classes) across Spain	Cross validation; Pearson's correlation obs. vs. pred.	Could be included as part of an ensemble approach to test standardized hunting data	Failure to adequately standardize hunting bag data
Vilaça et al. (2014)	Species presence-only (GBIF; Melis et al. (2006)); Environment (climate, land cover, vegetation, snow cover)	SDM (MaxEnt)	2.5 arc-minute resolution (approx. 1km) map of relative likelihood of presence across Europe	Cross validation; AUC (0.8); MESS (>0)	Already included as part of suite of SDMs in ensemble	Lack of process for conversion from likelihood of presence to abundance (relative or absolute)

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
Alexander et al. (2016)	Species range (GBIF; IUCN; EMMA; NBN; MAIB); Species abundance (regional); Hunting bag (regional); Environment (land cover, climate, topology, vegetation, agriculture, anthropological)	Expert classification to define presence/absence within report range; Assignment of classified abundance from hunting bag; Machine learning model (Random Forest) to predict based on environment	3 maps at 1km resolution across Europe reflecting: probability of presence; percentage of suitable habitat where presence is recorded; classified abundance index	None explicitly reported	Direct application as part of ensemble using standardized hunting bag data	Use of unstandardized hunting bag data; No justification for choice of model; Uncertain accuracy at chosen output resolution; Unvalidated
Jordt et al. (2016)	Land cover (DNEP)	Expert classification with classes assigned values 0-2 and then aggregated	2km resolution maps of relative suitability across Denmark	Comparison with sightings data	Validation of data driven model	Lack of repeatability and flexibility to incorporate new information from data collection
Bosch et al. (2017)	Land cover (GLOBCOVER); Species range (IUCN, WWF, EMMA)	Expert classification of 23 classes assigned values 0 (absent), 0.1, 1, 1.5 or 2 (most suitable)	300m resolution map of relative habitat suitability (assumed to reflect abundance) across Eurasia	Agreement between classification score and density of boar sightings	Validation of data driven model	Lack of repeatability and flexibility to incorporate new information from data collection

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
Croft et al. (2017)	Species presence-pseudo-absence (NBN); Species density (literature); Environment (climate, land cover, topology, anthropogenic)	SDM (Ensemble with 7 models) to predict suitability then regression to relate scores with density	10km and 1km resolution maps across GB reflecting: suitability (relative likelihood of presence) and abundance	Cross validation; AUC (0.8 and 0.7 respectively)	Direct application as ensemble framework to predict suitability from presence data and benchmark with available abundance data	Concern that suitability may not directly reflect abundance as different factors may be important
Pittiglio et al. (2018)	Species range (IUCN + national); Species abundance (Eastern Europe); Hunting bag (Western Europe); Environment (climate, topography)	Bioclimatic stratification with geospatial regression (trend analysis)	5km resolution map of density across Eurasia	Independent validation using (Melis et al. 2006); high levels of accuracy shown	Could be reproduced with new data as part of a complementary ensemble method or for validation; Could be combined with SDMs to include data derived dist.	Dependent on available data may involve unnecessary levels of inference and interpolation; does not consider unequal hunting effort
ENETWILD-consortium (2019)	Suitability maps (based on available data on wild boar occurrence obtained from GBIF) at 10 km square resolution	A Two-parts exploratory process: occurrence data to predict maps of wild boar suitability using an ensemble	100 km ² resolution: Predicted habitat suitability for wild boar; 0-1 scale. Predicted density of wild boar; 0-200 per	No cross-validation. Suitability resulting scores estimates were related with the density	Preliminary modelling The produced outputs of prediction of habitat suitability or presence/a	Lack of validation, scarcity of density values

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
	and initial version of abundance models based on hunting statistics at NUTS3 and NUTS2 resolution, that were statistically downscaled for MSs to 10x10 km grid squares	methodology combining output from a suite of independent SDMs including MaxEnt, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest and GLM, then relating the resulting suitability scores with a more limited number of corresponding density estimates to establish a relationship for their conversion	100 km ² with more intense colours indicate higher density		absence were used to underpin models based on available abundance data (hunting bag, census or density)	
ENETWILD-consortium (2019a)	Occurrence data to fit presence-only and presence-background models was sourced from GBIF and through the ENETWILD	A preliminary model analysis was performed to estimate the likely distribution of wild boar comparing the performance of a	Downscaling 10x10 km ²	Cross-validation method, using 75% of the data selected	Based on the fit and predictive accuracy of the distribution models tested here (biodclim and MaxEnt) it is clear that their	The volume and quality of available data (occurrence/hunting/density)

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
		presence-only model (bioclim) and presence-background model (MaxEnt).			performance is enhanced by the addition of data on survey effort, in this case derived from presence records of other associated species	
ENETWILD-consortium (2019a)	Updated suitability map for wild boar presence based on additional occurrence data and new algorithms, and new models based on high-resolution hunting yield data for MSs and neighbouring countries. The goals of this report are to further model the distribution and abundance	Five different algorithms to predict the environmental suitability, relative likelihood of presence, for wild boar across the study area as follows: a bioclim model based on the presence data alone; a Maxent model with a background sample of the	Downscaling 10x10 km ²	Occurrence: assess the predictive accuracy of each model using cross validation, repeated trials stochastically reserving a proportion of the complete datasets for testing and refitting model prediction	Maxent and random forests identified as the best candidate algorithms for modelling wild boar occurrence. The new hunting yield model solved the main drawbacks that were detected in previous analysis due to the incorporation of new data, variables	Results showed no consensus for a single best occurrence model: out of those tested, both Maxent and random forest could be considered the best options depending on the choice of assessment metric. There remain some methodological

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
	<p>of wild boar and to identify strategies to improve model outputs, providing updated suitability maps for wild boar presence. New environmental variables closely associated with wild boar abundance and distribution were also included</p>	<p>landscape comprising presence and absence locations; a support vector machine (kSVM); a random forest; and a standard logistic regression (Generalised Linear Model, GLM) model. The ecogeographical predictors more relevant in explaining the hunting bags were determined using generalised linear models, with a negative binomial distribution (to control the overdispersion in the data) and a logarithmic link function</p>		<p>ns with what remains, to compute three metrics. Hunting bags: The model was trained using an 80% random sample of the data and model predictions were validated against the remaining 20% of the data</p>	<p>and the use of smaller territorial units</p>	<p>adjustments. The predictive performance of the hunting yield model was high. Although the incorporation of new data at higher spatial resolution markedly improved predictions, such data is still needed in some regions, ideally coupled with hunting effort</p>

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
ENETWILD-consortium (2019b)	Updated suitability map for wild boar presence based on additional occurrence data and new algorithms, and new models based on high-resolution hunting yield data for MSs and neighbouring countries. New environmental variables closely associated with wild boar abundance and distribution were also included.	Occurrence: Using the rearranged variables and the complete occurrence (presence-absence) datasets we fitted five different algorithms to predict the environmental suitability, relative likelihood of presence, for wild boar across the study area as follows: a bioclim model based on the presence data alone; a Maxent model with a background sample of the landscape comprising presence and absence locations; a	Downscaling 10x10 km ²	Occurrence: assess the predictive accuracy of each model using cross validation, repeated trials stochastically reserving a proportion of the complete datasets for testing and refitting model predictions with what remains, to compute three metrics. Hunting bags: The model was trained using an 80% random	Maxent and random forests are the best candidate algorithms for modelling wild boar occurrence. The new hunting yield model have solved the main drawbacks that were detected in previous analysis due to the incorporation of new data, variables, and the use of smaller territorial units	Results showed no consensus for a single best occurrence mode. Predictions from occurrence and hunting yield models are statistically associated but differed among algorithms used to model species occurrence as well as among bioregions. Without additional data collection in the eastern bioregion, it is difficult to improve occurrence model

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		support vector machine (kSVM); a random forest; and a standard logistic regression (GLM) model. Hunting bags: Two equivalent hunting yield models were parameterized: one, the simplified final model (with a substantially lower number of parameters) was used for further exploration and downscaling.		sample of the data and model predictions were validated against the remaining 20% of the data. The validation process showed a good predictive performance of the simplified final model being able to accurately discriminate 5 abundance classes		
Jasińska et al (2019)	Train collisions with ungulates Environment (railway infrastructure, land-use and habitat variables)	a) Predicting Local densities using generalized additive mixed models (GAMMs)	Wild Boar Density map based on spatial correlation of data Relative probability of train-	'leave-one-out' cross validation (LOOCV)	Train collision with ungulates could be an adequate source of information to enrich	Objective to model densities accurately, mainly be used as a proxy. Local densities not

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
		quasi-Poisson family from local densities reported in the hunting districts in 2012 to 2015. b) Potential drivers of increased risk of collisions of ungulates GAMMs with binomial error distribution	wildlife collisions		data modelling, if data providers agree to share this information	validated, no sampling protocol provided
Kafley, et al (2019)	Count data from Camera trap survey- to derive detectability-corrected local group abundance Environmental; distance from water sources, elevation, and normalized difference vegetation index	binomial mixture models Negative Binomial	animal/group-level probability of detection	100 replicate datasets and assessed fit using parametric bootstrap procedures.	applicability of binomial mixture models for estimating population abundance This approximation works for other species, so it may have potential to be used for other species.	Null model was the most parsimonious model for the wild boar. Possibly design, effort, covariable selection and scale should be reviewed for this species.

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
Belda et al (2019)	Camera Trap survey Habitat characterization and structure	Factorial Analysis + discriminant and logistical analyses to obtain predicting models	Probability maps 2x2 km	NA	discriminant and logistical analyses could be included in suite considered by ensemble. Core area metrics seem to be good predictors for wild boar habitat) quality	Absence of model validation to assess accuracy. Temporal scale and effort should be redefined
Vargas Amado et al (2019)	Coordinate occurrence casual observations and (pseudo-) absences. Environment: related to bioclimate, to topography, to vegetation, to land fragmentation, and to socio-economics	generalized additive model (GAM) multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS) flexible discriminant analysis (FDA) random forest (RF) support vector machine (SVM)	grid data 1x1 km as probabilities of presence	Split-sample cross-validation (80% training, 20% testing) and computing the areas under the ROC curves.	Could be included as part of an ensemble approach	
Podgorsky et al., 2019	surveillance data by the National Reference Laboratory for ASF	factors shaping the probability of ASF positive wild boar	The probability of ASF case increased 3 to 20% to population	NA	Potentiality to use and combine different	

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	Host density, landscape structure, human activity, and distance to previous ASF case	generalized mixed-effects models General additive Models (for time analysis)	density. probability was stronger at locations near previous ASF incidents. More likely to occur in forested areas, with the probability of detecting an ASF positive sample rising from 2 to 11% as forest cover around the sample increased from 0.5 to 100%.		sources of data	
ENETWILD-consortium et al 2020a	occurrence and hunting yield-based data	approach to handle the bioregion effect				
Croft et al (2020)	Simulations Assessing specific risk Variations in the prophylactic management of boar. Variations in reactive	Spatial individual-based Model	rate of spread of ASF of ~4 km/month within the core population at densities around 15 boar/km ² , reducing to	NA	IBM approach allows to capture individual variation in movement and population processes.	Parameter assumptions (behaviour responses to management) may bias the main results.

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
	management		nearer 2 km/month toward the population edge where densities were closer to that observed in Europe (5 boar/km ²).			No true validation provided
Economov et al (2020)	<p>Casual records 'Mammals of Russia' 50 × 50-km²</p> <p>Aggregate values harvest per federation member of the Russian Federation</p> <p>Long-term data on wild boar numbers based on winter census data</p> <p>Environmental: WorldClim 19, topographic, snow depth, MODIS</p>	<p>MaxEnt</p> <p>Comparing Harvest and abundance index with habitat suitability distribution</p>	<p>Good correlation between the abundance assessment by VNIIOZ and habitat suitability Regions where wild boar abundance indicators are dissonant</p>	<p>Occurrences validated with external data based on harvest and abundance index</p>	<p>Introduction of a spatial structure of suitable habitats into the calculations of the regional/aggregated wild boar abundances.</p> <p>Potential of diverse data sources to test integration strategies</p>	<p>Data availability currently limited</p>

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
Fanelli et al (2021)	Georeferenced data on the wild boars harvested including age-structure. Hunting effort index	Spatial distribution of hunted wild boars (Kernel density plots and linear models) Dynamics of the hunted wild boars (Time series analysis Sen's method)	Heatmaps and Kernel density plot of the harvested wild boars Population and effort trends 1996-2018	NA	Case study: how improving the quality of hunting data can help modelling trends	Requires georeferenced records Local context
Wevers et al (2021)	Camera trap survey grid of 2.5 x 2.5 km, 3 days event	Three step Model Occupancy Detectability Scale optimization Multivariable occupancy models	Spatial projection of probability of presence, based on the averaged top occupancy models	NA	Take advantage of camera trap records to improve data quality at local regional scale, to calibrate models Improves the processing speed and automation of data processing	Information is limited to regional or local scales.
Gamelon et al (2021)	Simulation counts body size-mass and assessment of reproductiv	Integrated population models for exploited populations	Estimates of IPM for parameters associated with demographic rates,	Comparing IPM's predictions to observed data	framework to quantify density dependence in both population dynamics	Require large amount of data on both recaptures and

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	the status of females shot by hunters.	capture-mark-recapture-recovery	population-level properties and detection.	Testing discrepancies from estimated parameters from the IPM and estimates obtained from independent analysis of CMRR and reproduction data. Determining the IPM's ability to make biologically realistic short- to mid-term population forecasts. Assessing the robustness to the model's assumption about the timing of life	and all underlying demographic rates. With potentiality to analyses with high relevance to population management	harvests of marked individuals (CMRR data)

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
				history events		
Vajas et al (2021)	Harvest data at fine resolution level and data about hunting effort (number of hunters, number of hunts per year, etc.)	Catch-effort model	Estimates of animal density and catchability depending on covariates	Goodness of fit (predicted vs. observed)	Allows to accurately estimate animal total density from harvest data	Require data about hunting effort at fine resolution level
ENETWILD-Consortium et al (2021b)	Camera trap survey for estimate wild boar density	Random encounter model	Data generated by camera trapping in 15 areas in Europe			
ENETWILD-Consortium et al (2022a)			Wild boar density data generated by camera trapping in nineteen European areas.			
ENETWILD-consortium, Illanas et al (2022b)	Only presence records and hunting yields of wild boar and other ungulates	Model the occurrence and hunting yield (HY) density of wild ungulates compare the output of occurrence with observed HY	Spatially explicit models of presence probability and relative abundance.	AUC, TPR, TNR and TSS for presence probability. Cross validation through calibration plots for relative	Accounting for predictor correlations when variable importance is inferred, limiting map predictions for species with	Correlation in predictors can be difficult to remove/control.

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
				abundance	restricted distribution.	
Allepuz et al (2022)	Data from the national competent veterinary authorities and covered all ASF-positive wild boar carcasses found dead. EU's Animal Diseases Information System (ADIS)	Bayesian hierarchical spatial model	Temporal and space-time patterns by country. Spatial Target areas in which it is more likely to find ASF-positive dead wild boars	NA	Improve data occurrence	Conditional mainly to ASF areas where data collection is reported
Ruiz-Rodríguez et al (2022)	Hunting bags and predictor variables related to geography, climate, and land cover	Negative binomial distribution was used for GLZ model calibration	Predictive abundance at Hunting state	Internal validation Independent temporal series	Models are generalizable and can be used for predicting general abundance patterns over new time periods and large scales	Limitation to be used at fine resolution. Limitation to consider population changes over time
Karami & Tavakoli (2022)	Conflict vs no conflict records from interviews. Detect conflict-prone areas in different	Classification and Regression Tree, random forest, MARS, and tree net.	vineyard-boar conflict potential Maps	AUC (~0.90)	Include human-wildlife conflict records as presence records of wild boar presence.	Conflict records as well as information on reporting bias should be needed

Document	Description of model inputs	Modelling approach	Model outputs	Model validation,	Main application of the model for ENETWILD	Factors limiting the use of this methodology by ENETWILD
	land use/cover types, topographic, vegetation, and human variables				Conflict mapping	
Salazar et al (2022)	Yearly hunting activity, the carcass persistence seasonality, and the specific landscape characteristics. Habitat fragmentation and landscape connectivity	Individual-based spatiotemporal stochastic model (simulation)	Habitat fragmentation and landscape connectivity were highlighted as important factors shaping ASF propagation	NA	Incorporate ecological processes such as intraspecific interactions, animal movement, disease spread, etc.	Data related to movement ecology, species interactions etc. are needed to parametrize the model
Fernández López et al (2022)	Wild boar-vehicle collisions Landscape, climatic...	Royle-Nichols model, using detection/non-detections of wildlife-vehicle collisions to model animal abundance	Spatially explicit abundance index and wildlife-vehicle collision probability index	Correlation of the abundance index obtained with raw hunting bags	Take advantage of highly available and free generated data	Require wildlife-vehicle collision data and road information in all countries.
Razenkova et al (2023)	Winter Tracks counts Environmental indices; Dynamic Habitat Indices	Multiple Lineal Regression	The duration of frozen ground without snow and the end of frozen	Check for quality in winter track counts due to Soviet Union	Check for spatial autocorrelation in residuals	Snow tracks only apply to snow covered areas. Field work and

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	Winter Habitat Indices Topography Human footprint		season were particularly important in Russia	collapse. Check for spatial autocorrelation in residuals by using correlograms		sampling size not available
Morera-Pujol et al (2023)	Presence-only from citizen science and presence absence records from surveys	Bayesian integrated species distribution models	Relative abundance index	Index assessed by comparison with independent abundance surveys and raw hunting yields	Integrating different data sources	Observational models should be developed before data integration to obtain a good performance